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Titolo della Tesi:

**INTEROPERABLE DIGITAL RIGHTS MANAGEMENT ON
STRUCTURED PEER-TO-PEER OVERLAY NETWORKS**

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Contents

Acknowledgements	1
Preface	3
Introduction	5
1 Trust and Security on Peer-to-Peer Systems	7
1.1 Introduction to Peer-to-Peer Systems	7
1.2 Structured Overlay Networks	8
1.2.1 Chord	10
1.2.2 Pastry	14
1.2.3 Content Addressable Network (CAN)	18
1.2.4 DHT Summary	19
1.3 One Way Hash Function Algorithms	20
1.4 Security issues and goals on Peer-to-Peer systems	20
1.5 Application layer	21
1.5.1 Authentication	21
1.5.2 Authorization	22
1.5.3 Confidentiality	22
1.5.4 Integrity	23
1.5.5 Non-repudiation	23
1.6 Network layer	24
1.6.1 Incorrect routing update	24

1.6.2	Partition	25
1.6.3	Rapid join and leave	25
1.6.4	Sybil attack	26
1.6.5	Eclipse attack	27
1.7	Analysis of efficient way for preventing spam in a media search engine	28
1.7.1	Pollution of content and metadata	28
1.7.2	Index poisoning	29
1.7.3	Anti-pollution mechanism	30
1.8	Trust enforcements for Peer-to-Peer collaborative crawling	30
1.8.1	Trust models	31
2	Design of Interoperable DRM System on Structured Overlay Networks	35
2.1	Use cases	35
2.1.1	Distribution of Content Items in a Peer-to-Peer System	36
2.1.2	Fair Peer-to-Peer marketplace	37
2.2	Requirements	39
2.2.1	System overview	39
2.2.2	Expected operational environment system constraint and performance	40
2.2.3	High level diagram of the system	40
2.2.4	Requirements on network infrastructure	41
2.2.5	Requirements on devices	42
2.2.5.1	Requirements on user-devices	43
2.2.6	Requirements on contents	44
2.3	Specifications	45
2.3.1	Architecture overview and preliminary design	45
2.3.2	Metadata representation and indexing	47
2.3.3	Metadata retrieval and query format	48
2.3.4	Content access and distribution	49

2.3.4.1	Content creation	49
2.3.4.2	Searching and consuming	49
2.4	Analysis of candidate solutions	49
2.4.1	Proposed solution	49
2.4.1.1	Bamboo	50
2.4.1.2	FreePastry	50
2.4.1.3	Comparison	50
2.4.2	Selected solution	50
3	Implementation of Interoperable DRM System on Structured Overlay Networks	53
3.1	FreePastry	54
3.2	Chillout	57
3.3	Indexing and Retrieving Rights Metadata	58
3.4	Application implementation	60
3.5	Application User eXperience	64
4	Similarity search on DRM	73
4.1	Introduction	73
4.2	Backgrounds	73
4.2.1	Digital Rights Management	74
4.2.2	Similarity Search	75
4.3	The metric space approach	75
4.4	The proposed solution of metric distance for license	76
4.4.1	IPR-based distance functions	77
4.4.1.1	Binary conditions	79
4.4.1.2	Numeric conditions	79
4.4.1.3	Term based conditions	80
4.4.1.4	Distance for sets	81
4.4.1.5	Metric distance	81

4.5	Significant use cases	82
	Conclusions	85
	Acronyms	87
A	SAPIR	91
B	DMP	93
C	DMIN.it	95
D	Chillout	99
	Bibliography	102

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¹<http://www.eurixgroup.com>

Preface

The work reported in the thesis has contributed to the standardisation work undertaken by the Digital Media Project by significantly extending the functionalities of the the Open Source Chillout[®] Software implementing the Interoperable DRM Platform specification.

This work has also been used in the Digital Media in Italia initiative to provide concrete examples of how Italy can “play a primary role in the exploitation of the global digital media phenomenon”.

Leonardo Chiariglione

Introduction

The aim of this work is the design of a software solution for the management of digital rights on a Peer-to-Peer Structured Overlay Network (SON), making use of open standards and enabling further extensions.

The thesis is the result of the research activity performed by the author within the following projects:

- Search in Audio-Visual Content using P2P Information Retrieval (SAPIR - EU-FP6-45128)
- Digital Media Project (DMP)
- Digital Media IN Italy (DMIN.it)

Chapter 1 presents a survey on security issues on Peer-to-Peer networks, focussing the attention on Distributed Hash Tables (DHT) with an overall discussion on core security goals, anti-spam techniques, pollution and index poisoning. This work is the result of the security analysis on DHT performed within the SAPIR project. The reader familiar with Peer-to-Peer networks and DHT terminology will find several well known concepts which will be used as a starting point for the discussion in the following chapters.

The original contribution of the author is presented in Chapters 2, 3 and 4.

Chapter 2 analyses an Interoperable Digital Rights Management (iDRM) System enabling the digital content distribution on Peer-to-Peer system, defining requirements and specifications, according to the DMP guidelines. This work was integrated in the DMIN.it activities and was published as DMP documents.

Chapter 3 presents a prototype implementation, which makes use of and extends the Chillout, the DMP reference software. It is completely decentralized and can be exploited in any MPEG-21 Right Expression Language (REL) compliant metadata representation. It also proposes a special technique for indexing rights metadata on DHTs, which is currently under a conference review. The indexing process is made up of two steps: few metadata are indexed on DHTs and the others are stored into the exchanged DMP Content Files (DCF), that could be figured out as wrapper of MPEG-7 and MPEG-21 metadata bundled together with the associated resources.

Finally, Chapter 4 presents an innovative approach for indexing and searching digital rights on distributed networks. The work has been presented to conferences and published as well. This approach treats the metadata expressing rights as metric objects, enabling similarity search on Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) attributes between digital items. The content base similarity search can help both the users to deal with a

huge amount of similar items with different licenses, and the content providers to detect fake copies or illegal uses. A software application implementation is under development.

The software written by the author for implementing the prototype is currently released under Open Source distribution². The aim of the author is that the iDRM Peer-to-Peer Application will be widely adopted and used, as well as improved, by scientific academies and researchers.

²Mozilla Public License, v1.1 - <http://www.mozilla.org/MPL/MPL-1.1.html>

Trust and Security on Peer-to-Peer Systems

Preface: *As described in the introduction, the contents of this Chapter are going to be published as a public Report of the SAPIR project, concerning the analysis of trust and security in structured Peer-to-Peer systems.*

1.1 Introduction to Peer-to-Peer Systems

This Chapter presents a survey on security in distributed networks, with special attention to structured Peer-to-Peer systems. A brief introduction to DHTs is given in order to have a good understanding of the context and of potential security risks. Hence the Chapter takes into account the network and the application layers separately because of the different security attacks to deal with.

We can define a Peer as a device working as client and server at the same time. A precise definition of a Peer-to-Peer system [1] was initially given by Oram [2] and furtherly refined in [3]: *"[a Peer-to-Peer system is] a self-organising system of equal, autonomous entities (peers) [which] aims for the shared usage of distributed resources in a networked environment avoiding central services"*.

We can classify Peer-to-Peer Systems into two main categories: structured and unstructured [4]. Figure 1-1 (taken from [4]) shows this classification with examples of different implementations. These systems were originally conceived around the year 2000, when the bandwidth became wide enough to enable other cooperation models than traditional client-server one.

Unstructured Peer-to-Peer Systems can be divided into two main generations. The first generation was implemented in two different ways, one very close to the client-server model with a central manager (superpeer), and one, at the opposite side, based on a fully de-centralized system, where the location of a specific item is unknown and has to be discovered dynamically. Examples of centralized systems are Napster [5] and BitTorrent [6], while examples of the de-centralized ones are gnutella0.4 [7] and Freenet [8]. All these systems have revealed points of failure and are no more used in the actual deployments.

After a few years, the second generation of Peer-to-Peer Systems appeared with the aim to improve the first generation, combining the powerful features of the centralized and de-centralized systems and is therefore referred to as Hybrid. Gnutella0.6, JXTA [9] and probably (but the source code is not public) the widely used Skype [10] are examples of second generation Peer-to-Peer Systems. Second generation unstructured Peer-to-Peer systems have a significant scalability limit given by the number of hops necessary to reach a resource.

Research has progressed in a new direction to solve this problem: structured Peer-to-Peer systems which are giving some kind of self awareness of the network. Hashing algorithms as well as simple hash tables have played a major role in helping the researches to solve this issue. The third generation of Peer-to-Peer

<i>Client-Server</i>	<i>Peer-to-Peer</i>			
	1. Resources are shared between the peers 2. Resources can be accessed directly from other peers 3. Peer is provider and requestor (Sesent concept)			
	<i>Unstructured P2P</i>			<i>Structured P2P</i>
	<i>1st Generation</i>		<i>2nd Generation</i>	
1. Server is the central entity and only provider of service and content. → Network managed by the Server 2. Server as the higher performance system. 3. Clients as the lower performance system Example: WWW	<i>Centralized P2P</i>	<i>Pure P2P</i>	<i>Hybrid P2P</i>	<i>DHT-Based</i>
	1. All features of Peer-to-Peer included 2. Central entity is necessary to provide the service 3. Central entity is some kind of index/group database Example: Napster	1. All features of Peer-to-Peer included 2. Any terminal entity can be removed without loss of functionality 3. → No central entities Examples: Gnutella 0.4, Freenet	1. All features of Peer-to-Peer included 2. Any terminal entity can be removed without loss of functionality 3. → dynamic central entities Example: Gnutella 0.6, JXTA	1. All features of Peer-to-Peer included 2. Any terminal entity can be removed without loss of functionality 3. → No central entities 4. Connections in the overlay are "fixed" Examples: Chord, CAN

Figure 1-1. Overview and classification of Peer-to-Peer Systems [4]

Systems is actually built on top of DHT [11], that still represent an active and interesting research area. Nowadays we have several DHT implementation, such as Chord [12], Pastry [13], Content Addressable Network (CAN) [14], etc. and research is currently analysing how to deal with huge amount of multimedia items in DHT-based Systems in a scalable and efficient way. Since DHT has opened a new world for experimentation, a very powerful approach consists in applying a metric space to DHT, i.e. by providing Metric Content Addressable Networks (MCAN) [15] as well as Generalized Hyperplane Tree (GHT*) [16], Metric-Chord (M-Chord) [17], etc. We have to point out that the Network Infrastructure described in the following is mainly responsible for providing Contents in a distributed environment and for indexing and searching metadata in a suitable topology. We do not intend to provide a network enforcing content protection and government, since these issues are already addressed at the application layer as discussed below.

1.2 Structured Overlay Networks

A DHT is a hash table which is distributed among a set of cooperating computers which are referred to as nodes [18]. Data are distributed among a number of nodes and a routing scheme is implemented in order to allow the search of the node on which a specific data item is located [11]. *Lookup* is actually the main service provided by distributed hash table which returns (as standard hash table) the value associated with a

key. Hence a client provides a key to some node, which performs the lookup operation and returns the value associated with the provided key [18]

The other main service provided by DHT is the corresponding *insert* (or *put*) operation, which takes as input the pair $(key, value)$ and stores it on nodes, according to specific policies that differentiates DHT implementations. Even if the representation of keys and associated objects can be arbitrary, one-way hashing algorithms have been proved to be very useful for representing keys since they allows keys to be generated in a common way for whatever digital object we want to manage as bytes, text and audio/visual files.

A quick overview of this kind of function is provided in the following. DHT based Peer-to-Peer systems can support huge amount of data items and efficiently handle a very large number of nodes. However, due to limited storage/memory capacities and to the cost of inserting and updating items, it is unfeasible for each node to store all items locally and therefore each node is responsible for only a part of them [18]. This leads to the need of exchanging some information among the peers, i.e. the knowledge of which node is responsible for a specific key. This is accomplished by making use of *routing tables*, that contain pointers to other nodes known as *node's neighbors*. Every node in the system has a personal routing table, even if it doesn't store any item at all.

The management of routing tables is an important issue and several approaches have been proposed exploiting different routing algorithms. When a node receives a message for a destination *identifier* (ID) that it is not his responsibility, it forwards the message to one of the other nodes specified in its routing table and the process is repeated recursively until the destination node is found or a predefined number of forward operations have been performed. The choice of the next-hop node is determined by the routing algorithm and the routing metric [11]. For example, a metric could be some sort of similarity between the keys or could take into account the proximity between the nodes [19]. The design of routing algorithms and metrics minimizing node failures and incorrect routing information is a challenging research topic [11].

Nodes are connected each other over the existing network. Keys and routing tables constructing the DHT are maintained on top of this physical infrastructure. Hence DHTs are overlaying the actual systems and are named *overlay networks* (Figure 1-2 [11]). The real topology behind the DHT is the underlay network that can be a Local Area Network (LAN) as well as an internet Wide Area Network (WAN). We make use of the term *structured overlay networks* when an overlay network is created by DHTs.

Figure 1-2. Overlay and underlay view of Distributed Hash Tables [11]

As stated above, the routing algorithm is a core functionality of a DHT and it aims to decrease the number of re-routes, i.e. the number of hops that a lookup would take for reaching the node owning the searched key. Obviously reducing the number of hops decreases the time needed for lookups. Moreover, especially in our context, reducing the number of hops leads to a more secure infrastructure because we have to contact a smaller amount of nodes. Consequently the probability of having malicious nodes in the routing path is reduced as well as the vulnerability of the system. In order to reduce the number of hops, we have to add information to the routing tables.

For example a node, whose routing table has all the keys available on the DHT, does not have to forward messages, since the nodes to be contacted for every lookup are known. This extreme solution is infeasible due to the maintenance. Hence many algorithms have been developed for reaching the best trade-off between topology maintenance cost (related to the size of routing table) and latency (related to the number of hops). In a centralized system, for accessing a specific resource we have to contact only the node running the central server, thus solving every lookup in a single hop. In the opposite case, in a fully unstructured flooding system, every node has, in the worst case, to contact all the other ones because nodes haven't any routing table. DHTs instead can guarantee to find an item in a number of hops lower than or equal $\log N$. Different systems may however have a different base for the logarithm. In Chord [12] the base is fixed to 2, while in Pastry [13] it is variable: the base of the logarithm is 2^b where the parameter b is usually 4. Since the aforementioned systems, Chord, Pastry and also CAN are relevant for further discussion, they will be briefly overviewed in the following [20].

1.2.1 Chord

Chord [12] is the most famous proposal in the field of DHT systems. The Chord algorithm naturally provides a certain degree of load-balancing due to the use of a hash function that spreads uniformly the keys over the nodes. Chord is fully distributed because each node has the same functionalities, leading to a complete decentralization. The scalability of the system is achieved by the lookup function that is logarithmic in the number of nodes, thus enabling the management of very large systems. The availability of the nodes is guaranteed by the routing algorithm, which automatically adapts the routing tables during *join* and *leave* node operations.

Several applications can be built on top of the Chord layer such as cooperative mirroring, time-shared storage, distributed indexes, large scale combinatorial search and so on.

The Chord consistent hash function assigns a m -bit identifiers to each node and key by using a base hashing function like SHA-1 [21]. The node identifier is calculated, generally, as the hash of the IP address or the cryptographic public key of the node. Similarly, the identifier of a key is generated via the hash of the key. It is worth to underline that the size of m is a very important parameter in order to ensure a negligible probability of collisions. Exploiting a modulo 2^m consistent hashing, the identifiers are ordered in a ring topology. The successor of a given key k , denoted by $successor(k)$, is the node characterized by the identifier equal to or immediately subsequent to the identifier of k . If the identifiers are represented as a ring of numbers from 0 to $2^m - 1$, then the $successor(k)$ is the first node clockwise from k . In Figure 1-3, we sketch a system with $m = 3$. The ring is composed by three nodes, i.e. nodes 0, 1 and 3. Since the successor of the key 1 is node 1, this key is therein stored. Similarly, key 6 is inserted into node 0, whereas the key 2

Figure 1-3. Example of consistent hashing: in a the system ($m = 3$) containing three active nodes, we insert the keys $k_1 = 1$, $k_2 = 2$ and $k_3 = 6$ respectively in the nodes 1, in fact $\text{successor}(1) = 1$, 3 since $\text{successor}(2) = 3$ and 0, in fact $\text{successor}(6) = 0$.

into node 3. One of the most important property of consistent hashing is the ability of minimizing disruption in the case of joining or leaving of a node. When a given node n joins the network, some keys that were previously assigned to the successor of n become assigned to n . Conversely, when n leaves the system, all resources are reassigned to its successor. These are the only operations that we have to be performed in order to manage node joining and leaving.

Moreover, it can be proven [22], that for any set of N nodes and K keys, with high probability we have:

1. Each node is responsible for at most $(1 + \epsilon) \times \frac{K}{N}$ keys
2. When a node joins or leaves the network, $O(\frac{K}{N})$ keys change the responsibility value.

where $\epsilon = O(\log N)$ [22].

Key location

In the following we focus on the implementation of the lookup function in Chord, with particular attention to the state to be maintained by a peer in order to correctly find the responsible node for a given key. A very simple strategy is to store only the successor nodes in the ring. Of course, the inefficiency of this scheme is glaring: in the worse case it can require traversing the entire N nodes. In order to speed up the lookup process, Chord maintains an additional *finger table* which is a sort of routing table with (at most) m entries, where m is the number of bits of the identifiers. The i^{th} element of the table at node n contains the first node, indicated by s , that succeeds n by at least 2^{i-1} on the ring, with $1 \leq i \leq m$. In other words, $s = \text{successor}(n + 2^{i-1})$. We call node s the i^{th} finger of node n . The first finger of a node is called the successor of n .

The scheme depicted has some important consequences as each node stores information about a small

fraction of node. Moreover, it knows more about peers closer in the ring rather than about nodes farther away. Also, generally, a finger table does not contain enough information to identify the successor of a generic key k .

In the case node n does not know the successor of an arbitrary key k , i.e. the node responsible for the key, the routing protocol has to be performed. The main idea is that a node that has an identifier closer than n to the key k , will know more about the node responsible for k .

Repeating this strategy, the node n learns some information about nodes closer to k .

Figure 1-4 depicts an illustrative example where node 3 wants to find the node responsible for key 1. Since key 1 belongs to the circular interval $[7,3)$, the node contacts the peer in the third line of the finger table, i.e. the node 0. Similarly, key 1 in the finger table at node 0 belongs to the interval $[1,2)$, then the next node to contact is the node 1, i.e. the node responsible for the searched key. From the scheme described above

Figure 1-4. Finger tables and key locations for a network with nodes 0, 1 and 3, and keys 1, 2 and 6. The diagram shows the routing path created when the peer 3 generates a lookup for the key 1

we can state that with high probability the number of nodes that must be contacted to find a successor in an N -node network is $O(\log N)$ [12].

Node join

A Peer-to-Peer system is characterized by a high dynamics: peers join and leave the system frequently and in an unpredictable manner. In a similar context, the main challenge is to protect the ability of the system to locate every key. In order to hit the mark, Chord guarantees the following conditions: each node successor is correctly maintained; for each key k , the node responsible for k corresponds to the $successor(k)$.

It is possible to demonstrate that in a N -Chord network $O(\log_2 N)$ messages are necessary to re-establish the Chord routing invariants and finger tables [12]. However, in order to simplify the joining procedure, the protocol maintains a predecessor pointer that is used to navigate the ring counterclockwise. The strong assumption in Chord joining procedure is that the node n must know at least an existing node s in the ring. When a new node joins the network, the protocol specifies the following tasks to be performed:

1. Initialize the predecessor table and the fingers of node n . The peer n asks s to look them up.
2. Update the fingers and the predecessor regarding the addition of n .
3. Transferring keys. Once the node n is entered in the system, it is necessary to move responsibility for all the keys for which n is now the successor.

Figure 1-5. Finger tables and key locations after a join and leave procedures

Figure 1-5 shows the snapshot of the ring when the node 6 joins the system. It is worth noting that such algorithm is valid for non concurrent joining. On the contrary, in a Peer-to-Peer system characterized by a high turn over and dynamism on peers on-off time, we need to deal with a massive parallel joining of nodes, along with the problems regarding the failure and the voluntary leave of peers. The stabilization procedure described in the next section is intended to resolve these significant issues.

Stabilization procedure

Every node in a Chord ring runs the stabilization function periodically in order to keep node successor

pointers up to date and to ensure the correctness of the lookup operation. As a simple example, suppose node n joins the system, and its identifier stands between nodes p and s . n would acquire s as its successor. Node s , when notified by n , would acquire n as its predecessor. When p runs the stabilization procedure, it asks s for its predecessor (which is now n); p would then acquire n as its successor. Finally, p notifies n , and n acquires p as its predecessor. At this point, all predecessor and successor pointers are correct.

A meaningful situation is represented by a node failure: when a peer n fails, nodes whose finger tables contain n need to know the n successor in order to correctly update its state. For the purpose of simplifying this procedure, each Chord node maintains a successor list of its nearest successors on the ring. If a node n becomes aware that its successor has failed, it replaces the node with the first alive successor present in the successors list. In this manner, node n can forward lookup messages for keys the failed node was responsible for, to the new successor. Moreover, the stabilization procedure will adjust finger table and successor list entries that previously pointed to the failed node.

1.2.2 Pastry

The Pastry [13] overlay can be figured out as an extension of Chord. Each node receives an identifier of 128 bits uniformly distributed from 0 to $2^{128} - 1$. The main change with respect to Chord is the base of the logarithm for the routing table: in Pastry, the base is given by $L = 2^b$ where b is a configuration parameter usually equal to 4.

Compared to Chord, the number of hops are decreased, even if, at the same time, we have an increase in the cost of management. The main idea behind Pastry is to route messages to the node whose node ID is numerically closest to the desired key. In each routing step, a node normally forwards the message to a node whose node ID shares with the key a prefix that is at least one digit (or b bits) longer than the prefix that the key shares with the present node ID.

If no such node is known, the message is forwarded to a node whose node ID shares a prefix with the key as long as the current node, but is numerically closer to the key than the present nodes id. With this mechanism in a network made up of N nodes, Pastry can reach the node responsible for a given key with less than $\log_L N$ hops, which is the dimension of the routing table where N is the number of nodes.

As stated above, this reduction in the size of the routing table requires some more information in Pastry management, actually three data structures: the *routing table*, the *leaf set* and the *neighborhood set*.

The routing table is composed by $\log_L N$ entries. Each row of the routing table is made up of $L - 1$ entries containing the IP address corresponding to the node ID, as shown in Figure 1-6.

The leaf set is split into two parts each containing $\frac{L}{2}$ entries:

- the set of nodes with the numerically closest larger node IDs,
- and the set of nodes with numerically closest smaller node IDs,

relative to the present node ID.

Finally, the neighborhood set stores the node IDs (and the relative IP address) of M nodes (where M is commonly taken equal to $2 \times L$) that are closest to the considered node with respect to a proximity metric. In the following there is a description of the routing, node join and leave operations in Pastry.

0	1	2	3	4	5		7	8	9	a	b	c	d	e	f
x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
6	6	6	6	6		6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
0	1	2	3	4		6	7	8	9	a	b	c	d	e	f
x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6		6	6	6	6	6
5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5		5	5	5	5	5
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9		b	c	d	e	f
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
6		6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
5		5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
a		a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a
0		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	a	b	c	d	e	f
x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Figure 1-6. Routing table of a Pastry node with node ID $65a1x$, $b = 4$. Digits are in base 16, represents an arbitrary suffix. The IP address associated with each entry is not shown

Routing

The routing scheme in Pastry belongs to the family of *key – based* routing since the forwarding strategy depends on the value of the key to be found along with the node IDs of the existing nodes. Let k be the key in a lookup message.

If k falls within the range of node IDs covered by the leaf set, the message is forwarded directly to the destination node, namely the node in the leaf set whose node ID is closest to the key (possibly the local node). On the contrary, if the key is not covered by the leaf set, the message is forwarded to a node that shares a common prefix with the key by at least one more digit. This information is extracted from the routing table.

In certain cases, it is possible that the appropriate entry in the routing table is empty or the associated node is not reachable, so the message is forwarded to a node that shares a prefix with the key at least as long as the local node, but numerically closer to the key. Figure 1-7 depicts an example in which the node $65A1FC$ is looking for the key $D46A1C$ in a typical Pastry ring.

This routing procedure always converges, because each step takes the message to a node that, regarding the node ID of the local node, either:

1. shares a longer prefix,
2. shares as long a prefix with, but is numerically closer to the key.

Performance studies concerning the routing procedure show that the expected number of routing steps is $\log_L N$, assuming accurate routing tables and no recent node failures.

Node join

When a new node X wants to join the system, it needs to initialize its state and inform the other peers of its

Figure 1-7. Example of the Pastry routing procedure. Routing a message from node 65A1FC with key D46A1C. The dots depict live nodes in Pastry's circular namespace [13].

presence. The assumption is that the incoming node knows at least a bootstrap node A in the living Pastry ring that is near to X according to the proximity metric. X then asks A to route a specific join message. As any message, the routing protocol forwards the message to the existing node, namely Z , whose node ID is numerically closest to X .

In response to the join message, all nodes met in the path from A to Z send their routing table, leaf and neighborhood sets to X . Therefore, the incoming node updates its state depending on the information received. Moreover, it can request additional knowledge regarding other nodes.

Hence X notifies any nodes about its arrival in order that they can correctly update their state. Since node A is assumed to be in proximity to the new node X , A neighborhood set is exploited to initialize X neighborhood set. Moreover, Z has the closest existing node ID to X , thus its leaf set is the basis for X leaf set. Considering the general case where X and A do not share any common prefix, the row X_0 is initialized with the values present in the row A_0 .

In fact, since these values do not share any prefix with A , for transitivity, they do not have any prefix in common also with X . Otherwise, the row X_1 is generated by the row B_1 , where B is the first node encountered along the routing path. In general, the row M_i , where M is the i^{th} node across the routing path, concurs to initialize the row X_i of the incoming node.

Furthermore, the leaf set of the node X is built from the leaf set of Z , since Z is the node numerically closest to X , and the neighborhood set derives from the node A whereas it was selected on the base of a proximity criterion. Finally, X sends a copy of its state to each node present in the neighborhood and leaf set, and in the routing table, so as they can update their state in function of the new arrival. The cost of the join procedure, in terms of the number of messages exchanged, is $O(\log_L N)$ [13].

It is worth noting that Pastry uses an optimistic approach to face the problem of concurrent joins and leaves.

If the number of arrivals and departures of nodes affects only a small fraction of the overall nodes, this optimistic approach can be valid. In order to manage this problem, Pastry attaches a timestamp to each message containing state information exchanged among nodes.

Node leave

In the case a node fails or leaves the system voluntary, it is necessary to update the state of nodes that maintain references to inactive peers. Each Pastry node periodically sends a message in order to check the state of nodes in the leaf set. In order to replace a failed node in the leaf set, its neighbor in the node ID space contacts the live node with the largest index on the side of the failed node, and asks that node for its leaf table.

From the received information, that probably will be overlapped with the leaf set of the answering node, the peer will select the most appropriate one, verifying that it is alive. This procedure guarantees a valid solution unless $\frac{L}{2}$ nodes with adjacent IDs fail at the same time which is a very unlikely condition due to the property of node IDs generation.

The failure of a node that still appears in the routing table of another node is detected when that node attempts to contact the failed node and gets no response. To repair a failed routing table entry R_l^d , a node contacts first the node referred to another entry of the same row, namely R_l^i with $i \neq d$. In the case that none of the entries in row l have a pointer to a live node with the appropriate prefix, the node next contacts an entry in the next row, with R_{l+1}^i where $i \neq d$.

This procedure is likely able to find a valid substitute in the routing table if it exists. Even though the neighborhood set is not directly used in routing decisions, it is important to maintain it up to date in order to take advantage of proximity information. For this purpose, each node tries to contact the nodes in neighborhood set periodically to see if they are still alive. If a node does not respond, the peer asks other members for their neighborhood set and, after calculating the distance of each of the new nodes, it updates its table consequently.

Proximity concept

The concept of network proximity is based on a scalar proximity metric, like the number of IP routing hops or a geographic distance. To compute this distance estimation some network services such as traceroute or Internet subnet maps could be used. We suppose that each application on top of Pastry overlay implements this function depending on a selected metric and that a smaller value corresponds to a more desirable condition.

In [13] the authors underline that the proximity space should be Euclidean, i.e. the triangular inequality should hold between Pastry nodes. Indeed, several metrics, for instance the number of IP routing hops in the Internet, are not Euclidean: this does not impact the basic routing protocol, but it affects the Pastry locality properties. In order to improve the efficiency of the routing protocol, it is necessary to hold true the property that each entry in a generic row of the routing table contains the most nearest nodes (depending on the proximity metric selected) with respect to all possible nodes that share the same common prefix. Assuming that this property is valid in an existing network, it is possible to demonstrate that the joining of a new node maintains it true [13].

Even though the Pastry routing algorithm does not ensure the discovery of the minimal path, it selects a good route in terms of the proximity metric selected. This is useful in applications such as storage management, e.g. PAST [13] [23], because retrieving a file from a nearby node minimizes client latency and network load.

Figure 1-8. Example of a CAN network in a 2 – dimensional space, i.e. $d = 2$, initially with 6 nodes (from A to F) [14]

1.2.3 Content Addressable Network (CAN)

Also the Content Addressable Network (CAN) [14] is based on the concept of a distributed hash table. The basic operations performed by CAN are insertion, lookup and deletion of (key, value) pairs in an Internet-scale hash table. CAN uses a virtual d -dimensional Cartesian coordinate space to store (key, value) pairs that could be figured out as a hypercube. The zone of the hash table that a node is responsible for corresponds to a portion of this coordinate space.

Every key k is, therefore, deterministically mapped, by means of a uniform hash function, onto a point P in the coordinate space. A (K, V) pair is then stored at the node that is responsible for the zone within which point P stands. In Figure 1-8(a) an example of a 2 – dimensional CAN space with 6 nodes is shown. Point P belongs to the zone which node F is responsible for. To retrieve the entry corresponding to K , any node can apply the same deterministic function to map K to P and then retrieve the corresponding value V from P . If P is not owned by the requesting node, the request must be routed from node to node until it reaches the node whose zone P lies in.

CAN nodes maintain a routing table containing the IP addresses of nodes that hold zones contiguous to their own, to enable routing between arbitrary points in space.

Intuitively routing in CAN works by following the straight line path through the *CartesianSpace* from source to destination coordinates. Figure 1-8(a) shows the path between node A and point P (in zone F): it is possible to note that the route follows adjacent zones, in our example from A , going through zone D , and, at last, reaching zone F .

New nodes that join the CAN system are allocated their own portion of the coordinate space by splitting the allocated zone of an existing node in half, as follows:

1. The new node identifies a node already existing in CAN, using some bootstrap mechanism as in [24].
2. Using the CAN routing mechanism, it randomly chooses a point P in the space and sends a join request to the node whose zone contains P . The zone will be split, and half will be assigned to the new node.

3. The new node learns the IP addresses of its neighbors, and the neighbors of the split zone are notified so that routing can include the new node.

Figure 1-8(b) shows how the CAN space changes in regard to the arrival of a new node. Let us observe the disjunction of the zone E in order to give place to joining node G . When nodes leave CAN, the zones they occupy and the associated hash table entries are explicitly transferred to one of their neighbors.

Under normal conditions a node sends periodic update messages to each of its neighbors giving its zone coordinates, list of neighbors and their zone coordinates. If there is a protracted absence of such an update message, the neighbor nodes realize there has been a failure, and initiate a controlled takeover mechanism. If many of the failed nodes neighbors also fail, an expanding ring search mechanism is initiated by one of the neighboring nodes, to identify any functioning nodes outside the failure region.

In [14], the authors propose a list of design improvements regarding different aspects of the protocol:

1. Use of multi-dimensional coordinate space for improving network latency and fault tolerance with a small routing table size overhead.
2. Better routing metrics, by taking into account the underlying IP topology and connection latency alongside the Cartesian distance between source and destination.
3. Overloading coordinate zones by allowing multiple nodes to share the same zone for improved fault tolerance, reduced per-hop latency and path length.
4. Use of multiple hash functions to map the same key onto different points in the coordinate space for replication.
5. Topologically-sensitive network construction, assuming the existence of a set of machines that act as landmarks on the Internet.
6. More uniform partitioning when a new node joins by preferring to split larger zones.
7. Use of caching and replication techniques.

1.2.4 DHT Summary

While there are significant implementation differences between DHT Systems, all of them support (either directly or indirectly) a hash-table interface of put (key,value) and get (key) [25].

We can summarize that the main properties of a DHT are scalability and the self-management of items and routing information [18]. We can state that DHT are scalable as regardless the number of nodes in the system, the maximum number of hops required to find an item is less or equal to $\log_2 N$. Also items are dispersed evenly because each node store on average $\frac{d}{N}$ items where d is the number of items in the DHT and N is the number of nodes. This leads to an high scaling functionality, because join/leave of a node requires redistributing on average $\frac{d}{N}$ items.

We can state that DHTs have *self-management* of items and routing information because during the join and leave phase, the routing information is updated to reflect new nodes and items are redistributed. Also

failure are automatically detected and routing information is repaired to reflect that and items are replicated for recovering.

Anyway, we have to point out that DHT systems are fine for fetching files or resolving domain names, but present an even more impoverished query language than the original, unscalable Peer-to-Peer systems [25]. Because you cannot apply for structured queries on DHT. These systems provide just key,value pairs insert and lookup features. On the opposite, the first generation of Peer-to-Peer systems let you perform complex and structured queries as they have a central server and on the application layer you can provide several query approaches.

1.3 One Way Hash Function Algorithms

Most of the security issues are accomplished making use of Cryptography, we briefly discuss one-way hash function algorithms used to implement the structured overlays.

The advent of one-way digitally signed hash algorithms opened up opportunities for both verifying data integrity and, to a lesser extent, protecting data through obfuscation [26]. Nowadays, we can assert that these algorithms have also opened up the opportunity for structured overlay networks. In order to reduce collisions in the names used for keys in DHT, researchers have chosen a one-way hash algorithm for translating strings-keys into a some more unique identifier. One way hash functions are algorithms that take as input a message (any string of byte, such as a text string, a Word document, a jpg file) and generate as output a fixed-size number referred to as the hash value or message digest.

This size depends on the algorithm used and it is usually between 128 and 512 bits (as SHA-512 [21]). We have many implementation of DHTs as Chord making use of 160 bit for keys as well as Pastry, with 128 or 160 bit. Regardless the initial purpose of a one-way hash function was to create a short digest used to verify the integrity of a message in the security environment, in our DHT context it is used primarily for representing the keys of the Hash Table. The most important (but there are several) algorithm implementing one-way functions are MD5 and SHA-1. MD5 [27] was created by Ron Rivest (of RSA fame) in 1992 at MIT and produces a 128-bit hash value, while SHA-1 [21] was created by the National Institute of Standards and Technologies (NIST) in 1995 and produces a 160-bit hash value. SHA-1 is slower to compute than MD5 but is considered stronger because it creates a larger hash value. Some DHTs implementation make use of both in order to improve performances creating temporary keys quickly.

Encryption algorithms such as symmetric ciphers have evolved from the government-endorsed DES (Data Encryption Standard), a mainstay from the seventies through today in many government and commercial systems, to the latest algorithms such as RC4, IDEA, Blowfish, and AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) the newly government-endorsed with the winner algorithm Rijndael, a block cipher with a key and block length of 128, 192, or 256 [26].

1.4 Security issues and goals on Peer-to-Peer systems

The security concerns can be divided between the Application and Network layers. We are starting with the description of the Application layer as it points out the basic issues of security, as the meaning of

authentication/identification and what should be taken into account in a Peer-to-Peer environment. Next, we consider the Network layer, trying to addressing specifically the structured overlay network security issues.

1.5 Application layer

An application operating on a network infrastructure has to guarantee the basic security requirements, in order to deliver trustworthy business services on top of it. In the context of structured overlay network the security is critical and absolutely necessary. A business application on such a network is exposed to security-related damage such as denial-of-access, exposure of confidential data, unauthorized transactions as the well know Man-in-the-Middle [28] [29] and Mashup vulnerability [30], identity theft and data corruption.

There are five main goals of information security that a business application has to address: authentication, authorization, confidentiality, integrity, non-repudiation [26]. Follow a more detailed description.

1.5.1 Authentication

First of all we have to distinguish between authentication and identification: usually this represents a common misinterpretation. Identification is the process of assigning an identity to a specific entity, and authentication is a process that verifies that a user's identity is truly what the user claims it to be [26]. In our context we can figure out several entity that need an identification. We have at least peers, logical devices and users and all of the associated logical software layers can run on the same physical object as a laptop personal computer. The first authentication process was built on passwords and there are many problems related. We can divide authentication approach at least in three as follows [26]:

- what you know
- what you have
- what you are

The first approach is based on the classical password (or PIN [31]) asked to the user to authenticate himself. Passwords are useful but originate several problems related to their management. People makes common mistakes as writing down passwords, using the same password for most of authentication systems with no care on their different security levels (web site for public domain trusted at the same grade of internet banking), making use of common personal data in the password as the birth date, names of children, that a brute force application can try to guess.

The second approach is based on what you have at the authentication time. Some of the systems running this approach give the user a SecureID [32], a special device synchronized with its counterpart owned by the accounting system. The user is asked to give the current SecureID generated at the time he is applying for authentication. Other examples are smart Card [33] or smart tags devices as RFID [34].

Usually the two approach, first and second, are combined together as you can experience in an ATM system where you have a card and you know a PIN or internet banking where you have a SecureID and you know

a password.

The third approach is recently used and we can suppose that it's about to grow in the next future. It is based on biometric data that we can acquire at least from [26]: fingerprint verification, retinal analysis, facial recognition, iris verification, hand geometry, voice verification, signature verification. Even if most give the impression of unfeasible approaches in common applications, nowadays many laptops have fingerprint verification device as well as built-in web cam for face recognition and such a system can as example authenticate itself in a peered network. There are also several plug-ins written for web browsers that allow interacting with the biometric devices as fingerprint scanner and cameras and we can cite at least two standards for managing biometric data: the OASIS XML Common Biometric Format [35] and the NIST - Common Biometric Exchange File Format [36].

Summarizing, if we have to guarantee high security level in our applications on whatever network infrastructure, we have to try to adopt a mixed approach, made up of at least two of the listed above, as examples coupling fingerprint and password or fingerprint and smart card or SecureID and password.

We have not taken into account the methods for protecting the passwords or PIN or the other proposed approaches. Usually the Secure Socket Layer is widely used for protecting these information and making use of asymmetric cryptography is possible to envelope them with the public key of the remote system which will be able to read them making use of its private key. This handshake is useful for protecting the authentication tokens but could not provide the authentication itself.

1.5.2 Authorization

The concept of authorization resides in the guarantee that an authenticated user will do only the actions that she/he is allowed to perform. Systems supporting authorization mechanism are asked to have a list of actions for each user and for each instance they have to deal with. Many systems usually make use at this purpose of Access Control Lists [37], lists that specify the access rights to items.

In order to simplifying the authorization management, we can put together more users with a similar behavior, defining Profiles and Groups. We can have grants as a specific profile (as example administrator) and we can also have access to different groups with different access rights. Unix Operating Systems have a built in authorization feature, supporting ACL at low level.

Usually the profiling has done at the application level and just after the communication protocol layer. As example, profiling on web applications takes place immediately above the HTTP protocol, with specific filters running on top of the web contexts, as the widely used tool ACEGI [38].

In a peered environment we have to pay special attention to the authorization issue because it is needed by every business applications.

1.5.3 Confidentiality

When data is passed over communication paths that may be open to unauthorized viewers it needs to be protected. This is the confidentiality concept. A wide variety of information falls under the category of sensitive data.

In a Peer-to-Peer system, we can have sensitive data coming out from shared contents or from the applica-

tions running on such a system. Usually we think about medical records or private information as sensitive data. In a peered scenario where users access several multimedia contents, a sensitive information is the consumption of the items itself. The cultural consumption [39] could be a powerful business and can be figured out as confidential information that the applications running on the network have to protect.

Also data deriving from log files related to the user's choices on digital items as well as the number of times she has played a specific item has to be considered sensitive data. In order to protect these data the application layer has to make them unreadable except than by authorized users. This is accomplished by using encryption algorithms, or ciphers, secrete ways of representing messages [26].

As we are dealing in an European context, we have to mention that a specific directive on Data Protection produced by the European Community [40] forces business applications to keep confidential all the personal data provided by users.

1.5.4 Integrity

The application running on the peered network has to guarantee that data (digital contents and related information) has not been altered by any unknown entity during it transit between peers up to the final user. A malicious peer can alter the routing (as described later in the network layer) and can access the digital contents exchanged by peers and alter it before it reaches the final destination.

In order for the receiver to be able to check the integrity of the data, the sender must transmit some additional information as checksum or Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC), employed by many protocols including TPC/IP.

CRC is an error-checking code that is widely used in data communication systems and other serial data transmission systems. CRC is based on polynomial manipulations using modulo arithmetic [41].

Anyway an intelligent peer can easily overcome CRC method, for example introducing a malicious code into the digital content and some other insignificant parts of the code in order to have the same CRC.

To foresee this behavior strong one-way hash functions have been developed that make it computationally infeasible to create the same hash value from two different inputs [26].

1.5.5 Non-repudiation

Non-repudiation is the concept of ensuring that a contract cannot later be denied by either of the parties involved. Non-repudiation means, for example, that it can be verified that the sender and the recipient were, in fact, the parties who claimed to send or receive the message, respectively.

The system has to be able to bind the user and the actions she does on data, in order to be sure that a specific change on data was done by a specific user. In our context we have to enlarge the concept of user taking into account devices as well as peers.

So far the only approach for supply the non-repudiation issue is achieved by using encryption. Specifically digital signature is mainly used for this purpose.

1.6 Network layer

In the network layer we are considering the topology of the system. As we are dealing specifically with DHTs we focus our attention on common security attacks that DHT exposes. In the following sections we describe different possible security concerns which can be produced by the presence of malicious nodes in the network.

Most of DHT security issues are based on changes of the routing management algorithm, i.e. the routing table and its related information. For example, a node can route a message to the wrong node, or misinform nodes which are performing topology maintenance [18]. Most of the techniques to prevent these types of attacks involve verifying invariants of the system properties [42], such as ensuring that routing always makes progress toward the destination [18]. Even if most of the security attacks only lead to DoS (Denial of Service) problems, there are specific attacks, such as letting multiple nodes join and leave the system very frequently, that can break down the system [43]. In the following we survey the major common security attacks that DHTs have to deal with.

In this section we describe the security concern due to the invalid lookup. It is produced by malicious nodes that iteratively forward lookups received by other nodes to an invalid or non-existing node (they can eventually forward the lookups to existing nodes chosen in a random way). The occurrence of these failing lookups negatively impacts the performance of the Peer-to-Peer network, being bandwidth consuming and obviously resulting in a lower lookup efficiency, since the requesting nodes stop sending their queries to other peers when the time-to-live goes to zero.

A DRM solution working on DHT will deal with this security issue by trusting well-behaving nodes, making use of a secure node identifier to contact other nodes. This approach has been extensively used in Chord [12] and is based on the creation of a node identifier by hashing the IP address and the port of a given node. Since the IP address and the port number are necessary to contact the node, in this way it can be easily verified if the correct node has been contacted. The main advantage of this approach is that it provides a validity check on the origin of a message sent to a node, while a possible drawback is a low performance due to the cost of signatures.

Hence the secure node identifier will be the SHA value of the pair IP:port, $\text{secureNodeId}=\text{HASH}(\text{ip}:\text{port})$. Of course it could be better to have some kind of SSL handshake, symmetric or asymmetric, certifying the node with a specific nodeId. Unfortunately that requires some kind of granting procedure for joining the network that is not feasible in a fully free context. It could be used in a protected environment, with predefined peers and well established configuration.

1.6.1 Incorrect routing update

In this section we consider an other kind of security threat, due to the corruption of the routing tables. In this case a malicious node can send invalid updates to other nodes producing the building of corrupted routing tables. This is a major issue for DHT based networks, whose nodes create their routing tables by consulting other nodes. If a malicious node is sending an invalid update, the routing table of the requesting node is automatically corrupted and its queries can be directed for example to invalid nodes.

Moreover this corruption propagates into the network because also well-behaving nodes provide wrong information to other nodes due to the corruption of their own routing tables. The combination of an incorrect

routing update and of an invalid lookup can have disruptive effects for the Peer-to-Peer network since the queries can be directed mainly towards nodes with high latency and low bandwidth.

In the literature it is possible to find different solutions for this kind of security problems. For example in CAN [14] the routing updates are made by taking into account the round-trip-time in order to favor lower latency paths in routing updates.

In Pastry [13] a quite simple approach is used to detect such corrupted routing tables: each entry in the tables must be preceded by a correct prefix, which can not be reproduced by malicious nodes. In this way routing tables with a high level of corruption can be easily detected. Other approaches have been proposed (for example it could be checked if every node in a given routing table is really reachable) but often they can affect the network performance and are not suitable for all situations.

1.6.2 Partition

In this Section we briefly describe a security issue due to the action of a malicious node which forces other peers to join a parallel malicious network. It can happen that a node contacts an other node in order to join a Peer-to-Peer network and this node is indeed a malicious one, so the starting node is actually joining a malicious parallel network. The goal of this parallel network could simply be monitoring the behavior of well-behaving nodes to run the same protocol as the correct nodes, in order to get access to the contents shared in the correct network.

By providing even the look up capability into the original network and having a node connecting both of these networks or having some original data from the legitimate one, this coalition of malicious nodes could manage to camouflage itself and its true intent.

A new node might feel itself well off in the network, whereas it is actually subject to observation of its actions which are supposed to be kept private. The use of public keys, though expensive, can establish some stronger identity than mere IP-addresses, which are subject to frequent changes. If a node has successfully joined a legitimate network in the past, it possesses certain knowledge about the network and possibly nodes that successfully answered its queries.

It can indirectly check the routing tables of other nodes, by performing random queries to gain knowledge about possible different views of the network than its own. Making use of a node certification mechanism, that provides secure nodeIds, this kind of attack is quite difficult to succeed.

1.6.3 Rapid join and leave

Structured networks like nodes in a Chord ring impose an additional burden on the available bandwidth of nodes. A considerable communication overload occurs, which makes nodes vulnerable in ways they would not be in a fully decentralized network like Gnutella [7].

Each instance of join and leave a structured network causes a DHT to rebalance its keys and the data among the nodes, which generates a considerable traffic load and degrades the performance of the system. In a Gnutella network this kind of overload is feasible with a sudden increase of search messages that will flood the network, as its search-protocol does not scale, so this condition would be considered standard. In DHT systems this excess of data transfer and control traffic would render the whole network inefficient and impair

the secure functioning of the system.

In a classic denial-of-service attack (DoS) where an attacker generates arbitrary packets and overloads a targeted node, it would seem as if the targeted node failed in a normal way. As every node in a DHT is responsible for certain data, some of it would be unavailable for a certain period of time. The possible damage here or in a decentralized Peer-to-Peer network will however seem much smaller than in centralized Peer-to-Peer networks like the former Napster or a hybrid Peer-to-Peer network with super-peers. By having the servers attacked with a DoS, whole portions of the network would be knocked out for a certain time.

In order not to become too suspicious to many other nodes at once and to make its own malicious behavior more difficult to detect, a node may behave well with some part of the peers in a network and follow the protocol correctly. In a DHT system those peers would be the immediate ones in the vicinity of the malicious nodes identifier space. In this way they are hardly discovered because they are in the same set of the identifier space of a malicious peer, but in this space they mimic to follow the correct protocol.

Good behavior with these peers guarantees, at least, longer connectivity to the whole Peer-to-Peer network, as these peers would keep the malicious node in their routing tables. Legitimate reports of bad nodes would not be distinguishable from false accusations of the good ones.

Public keys and digital signatures here would help gain some assurance in the legitimacy of the reports by having all peers sign their responses. In conclusion, a structured topology of nodes provides considerable improvement in performance of the network as well as sensitivity to abrupt changes in the protocol behavior due to the possible impact of malicious nodes.

1.6.4 Sybil attack

In this Section we describe a typical security concern for Peer-to-Peer networks which is usually referred to as Sybil attack [44]. In case of this kind of attack, a malicious node (or any other single entity on a network) obtains multiple fake identities and pretends to be multiple, distinct nodes in the system. In this way other nodes might believe in having an interaction with some distinct nodes whereas in fact there is only one entity they are addressing. Therefore by controlling a large fraction of the nodes in the system, the malicious user is able to replace the well-behaving nodes in collaborative tasks as shown in Figure 1-9.

Large scale Peer-to-Peer systems deal with security concerns related to faulty or malicious remote computing elements by employing redundancy. In Peer-to-Peer systems it is difficult to avoid a malicious nodes that masquerades under multiple identities and thus appears to be many different users. This implies that given particularly huge resources (bandwidth, disk space, computing power) some deceiving peer could gain control of a large part of a Peer-to-Peer network by undermining its redundancy, which is one of its basic properties. The primary solution for this kind of threats is that the system must ensure that distinct identities refer to distinct entities.

The solution proposed in [44] is to have a trusted agency which certifies identities, so that each node receives an identifier by a central server which is responsible of the distribution of all identities. In the absence of a central identification authority, the capability of a single node to discriminate among remote entities depends on the assumption that the resources available to the attacker are limited. Anyway this situation could be unrealistic for many Peer-to-Peer systems, because would require that each node operates under almost identical resource constraints and that all identities are validated simultaneously by all entities, coordinated across the system and as shown in [44] the Sybil attack is still possible with such systems.

Figure 1-9. *The sybil attack [18] [44] Node c gains majority by imposing as nodes c,d and e in the overlay network.*

Many possible solutions have been proposed so far against the creation of multiple identities in a Peer-to-Peer network. For example computational puzzles, like in HashCash [45], might be used. This is an old solution for defense from DoS (denial-of-service) attacks. Before joining the network a peer has to solve some computational problem, thus is forced to use his CPU-cycles needing more time to join than usual. But in the case of an attacker with huge resources, it would at best slow down the process of generation of false identities and the process of these virtual nodes joining the network.

In structured Peer-to-Peer networks like Chord and Pastry where the network determines different tasks that certain peers have to do, hashing of IP addresses is performed partly to establish some kind of identity of individual peers. This would surely complicate and prolong the process of a Sybil Attack.

Obviously the most intrusive method of binding an identity directly to a node would be, of course, to provide a distinctive identification for each computing unit that is taking part in a network. Many commercial platform are available providing cryptographic keys embedded inside of every hardware device. Of course a user has to implicitly trust that these devices have an embedded key (and not an arbitrary one) and the users actually use these as they are supposed to. The concept of Pretty Good Privacy (PGP) [46] web-of-trust may vouch for established identities for other newcomers in the network, but may also be misused by the malicious node to subvert the chain of trust. As a last resort for keeping all the possible weaknesses of the aforementioned solutions somewhat under control, one can rely on certification authorities and similar trusted agencies. The rationale behind the solutions described above is to limit the resources available for malicious nodes in order to reduce the probability of success in such attack.

1.6.5 Eclipse attack

In this Section we briefly describe a security issue referred to in the literature as Eclipse attack [47], which constitutes a more general attack on overlay networks than the Sybil attack described in Section 1.5. It is based on the activity of a malicious peer which keeps control of the neighbor nodes of one or more well-behaving peers and in such a way those well-behaving nodes are unreachable (eclipsed).

This situation is due to the fact that each node in the network maintains overlay links to a set of neighbor nodes. Each node uses these links to participate in the maintenance of the Peer-to-Peer network and to

keep its functionalities, so the correct communication among nodes exploits such overlay links to forward messages.

In case a malicious peer is able to control a large fraction of neighbor nodes of a well-behaving peer, all messages directed to that peer will be dropped or rerouted and that peer will become unreachable.

1.7 Analysis of efficient way for preventing spam in a media search engine

In the previous sections we have analyzed many malicious and opportunistic behavioral patterns that can be observed in Peer-to-Peer systems. Recently a new form of malicious behavior, namely, content pollution, has been observed in real Peer-to-Peer file sharing systems [48]. Pollution on peered networks is very close to the spam behavior that we usually experiment accessing web pages on http protocol. We can have different kind of **pollution**, specifically related to the **content** itself or to the associated metadata, discussed in section 1.7.1. Finally we can have **index poisoning**, discussed in section 1.7.2. Some techniques have been proposed for fighting pollution and in section 1.7.3 we have summarized the relevant ones for DHT systems.

1.7.1 Pollution of content and metadata

The pollution of contents is one of the most widely used sabotage technique.

One way to combat Peer-to-Peer file sharing of copyrighted content is to deposit into the file sharing systems large amount of polluted files [49]. The goal of the polluter is to trick users into repeatedly downloading polluted copies of the targeted title; users may then become frustrated and abandon trying to obtain the title from the file -sharing system[50]. Two potential strategies for polluting contents are **decoy insertion**, which consists of injecting corrupted copies of a file into the system, and **hash corruption**, which consists of injecting a corrupted file with the same hash code as a non-corrupted one [51].

Decoys are files whose name and metadata information (as artist name, genre, length, etc...) match those of the item but whose actual content is unreadable, corrupted or altogether different from what the user expects [52]. As Liang et al [49] have pointed out, we can classify the pollution into at least two main categories:

1. content pollution
2. metadata pollution

The former is the most common. The polluting party decoys for a specific digital content by modifying it in one or more ways, including replacing all or part of it with white noise, cutting the duration, shuffling blocks of bytes within the digital recording inserting warnings of the illegality of file sharing in the recording, and inserting advertisements [49].

The latter focus the attention to the metadata associated to the contents, trying to tamper them. This often involves taking an older recording, whose copyright has expired and changing its song title, album title, and artist name to that of the targeted recently-released recording [49].

With both of pollution techniques, the user will not be able to play nor search the digital item he is looking

for.

Recently, it has been observed that the fraction of polluted copies of popular files in KaZaa could be as high as 80% [49]. Nevertheless, the efforts towards reducing pollution dissemination have been very timid [48].

1.7.2 Index poisoning

The index poisoning is referred as the index alteration for spamming purpose on Peer-to-Peer systems.

Both structured and unstructured file-sharing systems are highly vulnerable to index poisoning [53]. It consists in inserting bogus records in Peer-to-Peer indices, making the system fail to locate an existing object [48]. This is also referred as hash corruption mechanism. The index in a peered systems is made up of IDs, a unique identifier usually obtained as result of a one-way hashing function, as described in section 1.3. Anyway, it could happen that two or more items will obtain the same ID.

Some of the common used algorithms generate the file ID based only on parts of the file [51]. In this context, a malicious peer can make changes on the parts of the file which are not used by the algorithm to generate the file ID, creating different files with the same file IDs. When a user request this file, will receive a list of versions of that file, each one with a distinct file ID and a certain number of copies [51]. Then, the user chooses a version, downloading pieces of different copies. If a downloaded piece is a corrupted part from the changed file, the entire download file will be corrupted [51].

FastTrack [54] network uses an algorithm called *uuhash*, which uses only some pieces of the content file to generate the ID [51]. This enables malicious peer to create the same ID for different contents.

Another way for altering indexes is to change client node of a peered network in order to compute wrongly the IDs, associating a corrupted file to the actual ID related to the correct keywords.

In a typical file-sharing system today, when an index receives an advertisement for a copy, the index does not authenticate the advertisement; specifically, it does not verify that the copy is truly available at the advertised location (bundle of IP address and port number). In the index poisoning attack the attacker falsely advertises copies of the targeted titles [53]. As described by Liang et al in [53] we can have false advertisements as follows:

- random version identifiers that do not correspond to any existing versions
- IP addresses that do not correspond to any nodes participating in the file-sharing system
- unavailable service port numbers at participating nodes

In Overnet DHT topology, if the poison index attack is generating random version of the identifiers, when a users searches for the keyword, the user's client receives the bogus identifier. If the user selects the bogus identifier, the DHT displays "looking" and searches indefinitely for the identifier [53]. Otherwise, if the attack is providing phantom couple IP-ports, the user will receive a timeout error message.

1.7.3 Anti-pollution mechanism

Some of the proposed solutions contrasting the content and metadata pollution are useful in the context of structured overlay networks and as Liang et al [49] have suggested, we can report at least the following two:

- **Reputation systems** In a reputation system peers assign reputations to each other aiming at identifying and isolating malicious users that actively disseminate polluted content in the network [48]. In their work, Costa et al [48] have presented **scrubber**, a new decentralized reputation system which simplifies the deployment of Peer-to-Peer clients, and captures the peculiarities of pollution in large scale systems. In **scrubber** there are two main components: the **Individual Experience** and the **Peer Testimonial** which captures the opinion of the other peers or the community.
- **Blacklists** This is the list of the polluter's IP addresses. Usually the anti-pollution systems try to identify IP address ranges that are broad and complete enough to cover the hosts providing the polluted content, yet narrow enough to exclude the vast majority of ordinary users [50].

1.8 Trust enforcements for Peer-to-Peer collaborative crawling

A possible technique fighting pollution and index poisoning, is to crawl the Peer-to-Peer system in order to obtain for each title of the shared objects the number of versions, copies, the IP address of the content provider and the metadata associated to the contents. With this information it is possible to set up mechanisms for identifying polluted contents as well as IP ranges of nodes that are poisoning indexes.

In a Web of trust environment [49], the user receives updated lists of friends from all of its own trusted friends. The user downloads from friends and from the friends of his friends. If the user receives polluted content from any friend of friend, the user ceases to download from him and notifies his direct friend of the problem. The idea is similar to the trust mechanism used in PGP, as discussed in section 1.6.4 [49].

In order to fight the pollution and the index poisoning, it is possible to set up an automatic crawling of the shared contents of the DHT, where peers are joined in social networks as described above, and where the trusting of peers/users involved in the SON drives the mechanism of pollution detection leading to an automatic identification of malicious peers as well as corrupted contents and indexes.

Recently many contributions have been proposed concerning the definition of trust models in a Peer-to-Peer environment, which are mainly based on the definition of an appropriate metric to establish reputation within a Peer-to-Peer network and achieve an efficient level of trust in the network.

Various metrics for reputation management in a Peer-to-Peer environment have been proposed (see for example [55] for an overview of different algorithms for metric definition). As already described before, the main problem of these kind of networks is the lack of a central authority that can guarantee and certify the quality of the shared resources and estimate the behavior of other peers.

Different solutions have been proposed to collect information and estimate metrics, describing the performance and quality of other peers, without resorting to a centralized service. The aim is the creation of a

distributed algorithm that is run by autonomous untrusted agents and that is sufficiently reliable, efficient and secure to be robust against malicious peers.

In general a peer, which needs to engage with another peer to perform some kind of transaction, could benefit from this approach in the selection of a peer which has the desired characteristics with respect to some metric and also to assign a rating based on the information coming from other peers. Data overlays and collaborative content distribution systems have a need for a distributed metrics evaluation mechanism. The first scenario where this approach can be applied is file sharing in a Peer-to-Peer network where a number of malicious peers provide corrupted data. The goal is to provide a quick access to a trustworthy source and above all to update and retrieve quickly trust ratings of peers. This requires the implementation of tools for distributing efficiently trust computation between a number of honest peers. The final goal is to implement a system that is able to alter the natural scheme of selection of the transacting peers in order to maximize the number of authentic downloads without unbalancing the load in the network.

EigenTrust is an algorithm proposed for file sharing in Peer-to-peer systems and has been widely used for the creation of metrics. In [56] the algorithm EigenTrust is introduced and a possible approach to aggregate the local trust assessments of all peers in the network in an efficient, distributed manner is discussed. Several issues related to practical aspects of keeping peers honest in EigenTrust are discussed for example in [57].

PeerTrust [58] is a novel algorithm that combines several parameters such as feedback from peers and credibility of the feedback source into a general trust metric. Guha and others [52] propose a framework for trust and distrust propagation on networks. More recently, in [59], a novel protocol called SybilGuard for limiting the corruptive influences of sybil attacks is based on detecting small cuts in the graph of trust relationships between peers. There is already ongoing work on incorporating the notion of trust into distributed ranking of Web pages. Specifically, the goal is to incorporate the concept of trustworthy peer in the meeting selection step of the JXP algorithm [60]. In [55] various metrics that can be easily integrated with EigenTrust to build a reputation system are described, in order to create a system able to assist agents in choosing a reliable peer to transact with when one or more have offered the agent a service or resource. A number of new attack models are introduced along with the creation of a new metric, called dishonesty, which results in a more effective way to reduce the amount of inauthentic downloads for all the cases in which EigenTrust alone is not sufficient. A first possible scenario is file sharing in a Peer-to-Peer network. The goal is to provide a quick access to a trustworthy source and above all to update and retrieve quickly trust ratings of peers. This might require the implementation of tools for distributing efficiently trust computation between a number of honest peers. An excellent taxonomy of concepts in Peer-to-Peer reputation and trust management is given in [61].

1.8.1 Trust models

The following is a survey on trust models, mainly taken from a very good analysis written by G. Weikum. In this section we focus on the currently proposed approaches for trust enforcement which can be found in the literature, which propose different solutions concerning various algorithms to be used for the implementation of a web of trust. A relevant work concerning trust models is [62], which describes a general framework for different types of trust and distrust propagation in a graph of Web pages, sites or other entities. One commonly proposed solution to this problem is to build and maintain a Web of trust, as already described

before, across the whole Web in order to allow users to express trust of other users, which can help users to develop an opinion of another user without prior interaction and give an estimation of the quality of information before acting on it.

The natural approach to evaluate the quality of information would be to collect together the opinions from different users, but this approach can give fake results due to the possibility for a user to express different opinions using multiple identities. Therefore recent works propose a mathematical approach to allow the propagation of trust, based on trust relationships among users as in the real world. The main advantage for this kind of web of trust based on trusted relationships, as already mentioned, is mainly the possibility to skim all the available data through the sources trusted by each user. On the other hand, in a business scenario well-trusted users can receive great benefits concerning their visibility and influence in the web of trust.

Moreover many recent works have pointed out that the assignment of trust by users is not enough to develop a model which is able to describe real situations in an accurate way. In addition to trust, users should also be able to express distrust (negative trust), which for real world applications is as relevant as trust. In [62] the development of a trusting algorithm which takes into account both trust and distrust is discussed. The main challenge is the modeling of distrust, to handle negative trust in a coherent way to determine a measure of trust from a node to an other one, because this introduces a complication in the mathematical approach and needs a careful handling of different issues, such as the propagation of distrust itself. The main challenge concerning the propagation of trust is due to the fact that if a user distrust an other one, the trust value the second user assigns to a third user could be no more reliable, since the value model of the second user could be very far from the evaluations of the starting user (and this could be the reason why the first user distrusted the second one), therefore no estimation about the third user can be obtained by the first user based on the trust rate of the distrusted second user. This simple consideration, applied to real world systems, shows the need for a reliable mechanism for distrust propagation.

It is worthwhile to notice that the management of distrust for the implementation of the algorithms has appeared in the literature only a couple of years ago, therefore many algorithms or approaches proposed in the past didn't attempt to model distrust in any way, but focused mainly on the comparison of different models on real, huge data set.

An other typical problem of web of trust is due to the fact that each user usually trusts only a limited number of other users and an alternative solution must be provided to the remaining users who were not assigned a trust value. In [63] different propagation mechanisms are studied which include a method for the prediction of trust values for users without an explicit trust rate. Link analysis on Web graphs and social networks form the foundation for authority assessment, search result ranking, and other forms of Web and graph mining. The PageRank method is the most widely known member of this family.

TrustRank [62] is a PageRank-like authority measure based on manually labeling a seed of highly trusted hosts, and then propagating that trust to other hosts. This algorithm allows estimating the amount of trusted score that each Web page receives and indirectly evaluating also the amount of score received by spammers. In [64] and [65], the original TrustRank idea has been further extended. Detecting and combating Web link spam is a special, but highly important case of reasoning about trust and distrust.

A taxonomy of the most important spamming techniques can be found in [66]. A number of algorithms have been presented in order to fight spam. Most of them (see, e.g., [64, 65, 67, 68, 69]) analyze the statistical

properties of the link structure induced by the Web and classify as spam those pages that exhibit statistically significant local deviations in these properties. The problem of untrustworthy or manipulated content is felt even more in a Peer-to-Peer environment. The complete lack of accountability of the resources that peers share on the network offers an almost ideal environment for malicious peers and forces the introduction of reputation systems that help to assess the quality and trustworthiness of peers. In [70], the authors present a complete overview of the issues related to the design of a decentralized reputation system. EigenTrust [56] is one of the first methods introduced to assign a global trust value to each peers, computed as the stationary distribution of the Markov chain defined by the normalized local trust matrix C whose element at position $[i,j]$ represents the local trust value that a peer i assign to a peer j . Extensions towards distributed and non-manipulable EigenTrust computations are presented in [57]. The anomaly detection procedure described in [71] analyzes peer activity on the network in order to identify peers whose behavior deviates from the typical peer-traffic profile (e.g., duration of connections, uploaded bytes, etc). In [72] the authors present SeAI, an infrastructure designed for addressing the problem of selfish peer behavior. It works by combining a monitoring/accounting subsystem, an auditing/verification subsystem, and incentive mechanisms. Another framework for reputation-based trust management is presented in [58], where peers give feedback about other peers' good or bad behavior and various forms of network-wide trust measures can be derived in a Peer-to-Peer-style distributed computation.

In [60] the JXP algorithm is presented. It can be used for computing PageRank-style authority scores of Web pages that are arbitrarily distributed over many sites of a Peer-to-Peer network. Peers are assumed to compile their own data collections, for example, by performing focused Web crawls according to their interests. This way, the Web graph fragments that reside at different peers may overlap and, a priori, peers do not know the relationships between different fragments. The JXP algorithm runs at every Peer, and it works by combining locally computed authority scores with information obtained from other Peers by means of random meetings among the Peers in the network. The computation on the combined input of two Peers is based on a Markov-chain state-lumping technique, and can be viewed as an iterative approximation of global authority scores. JXP scales with the number of Peers in the network. The computations at each Peer are carried out on small graph fragments only, and the storage and memory demands per Peer are in the order of the size of the Peers locally hosted data. It is proven that the JXP scores converge to the true PR scores that one would obtain by a centralized PR computation on the global graph.

Design of Interoperable DRM System on Structured Overlay Networks

Preface: *As described in the introduction, the contents of this Chapter have been published as DMP (Digital Media Project) documents [73, 74]*

2.1 Use cases

For the proposed solution we consider the following use cases: the distribution of Content Items in a Peer-to-peer network, named in the following **Controlled Peer-to-Peer Distribution use case** and the development of a business model which benefit from a high level of cooperation among peers named in the following **FairP2PMarketPlace use case**. In the use cases presented in this document, the following types of users are considered:

- Creator: the entity responsible for
 - creating a resource (a short movie, a song, etc.)
 - specifying the metadata, the rights information (the modalities according to which other users will be able to use the resource) and if necessary the protection information for the resource. Hereinafter, the structured bundle of this information is called the DMP Content Information (DCI)
 - wrapping the resource and the DCI in a file, hereinafter the DMP Content File (DCF)
 - ingesting the content item in the Peer-to-Peer network as a DCF
- Distributor: the entity owning the right to distribute a typically protected content item to other users or devices, according to the terms and conditions expressed in the license bundled to it.
- End-User: the entity owning the rights to use (e.g. play) a content item according to the terms and the conditions expressed in the license bundled to it. The end-User may have the capability to acquire the rights over a certain governed resource by performing some actions (e.g. make a transaction).
- A number of Service Providers, entities that may add value to content by providing services such as indexing, ranking, etc.

Any User part of the Peer-to-Peer network may play any of the roles presented above.

2.1.1 Distribution of Content Items in a Peer-to-Peer System

This use case is based on the Use Case and Value Chain No 6 - Controlled Peer-to-Peer Distribution reported in [75]. We imagine a Peer-to-Peer network whose members can have access to two kinds of Content Items:

1. Governed by means of a License only, without enforcement (called Open Release by the Digital Media Project)
2. Governed by means of a License and Protected by means of DRM Tools

We can focus on a particular situation where these Content Items are mainly music files. In case (1) we can imagine that the members of the Peer-to-Peer network can create and share their user generated music to be released as unProtected Items, e.g. with a License allowing for the free distribution within the Peer-to-Peer network, subject to Creative Commons-like licensing terms.

The members of the network are provided with a program to create and share their own Content Items. The Content Item is a DCI containing the License, the Metadata and the Resources (or a reference to them) and is stored in the shared directory of the member of the network as a DCF. The member associates a License to a new Content Item using a small number of standard templates, before ingesting the created DCF in the Peer-to-Peer network. The Metadata associated to the Content are used for indexing it in the Peer-to-Peer network. The other members can search for this Content using the associated Metadata and consume it according to the License. They could also browse the shared directory of the member who created the Content to possibly search for similar or related music files.

In case (2) the network can also host Content Items which are Governed by a commercial License and are possibly Protected by DRM Tools. We imagine that the members of the network, when searching for their favorite music, can find the Contents produced by a record company. The company has joined the network to promote and sell their repertoire or these Content Items. If a member of the network buys the Content Item, he may store it in the shared directory of his PC.

The members of the network can search for these Items in the network or can discover them "by chance" when browsing the shared directory of the other members. Content Items produced by the record company are Encrypted and can be consumed by the other members of the network only after they have obtained a License. A few of these Items could possibly be unEncrypted because the record company wants to use them for promotion.

The members of the network are provided with a program which is able to perform the following actions: searching Items, browsing the shared directory of a given member, identifying the License associated to each Item to be agreed before consumption, enabling the decryption of the Resource (if necessary) after obtaining the required key and playing the Content according to the License. It should be noted that the program provided to the members for this use case can be used also for the situation described in use case (1).

It should be noted that in this use case the members of the network only host Content Items provided by a record company with a commercial License. In the following section we imagine a use case where the peer are actively involved in the process of distributing such Content Items by defining a business model based on a high collaboration among peers.

2.1.2 Fair Peer-to-Peer marketplace

This use case models a scenario in which peers trade digital items over a Peer-to-Peer infrastructure implementing a profit-sharing, fair and high-collaborative platform [76]. With respect to the Use Case and Value Chain No 6 - Controlled Peer-to-Peer Distribution described in [75], this scenario differs from the following aspects:

- **Distribution model:** each peer (authorized to deliver the item) actively participates in the distribution process sharing his own physical resources (e.g., bandwidth, CPU cycles, storage space, etc). Therefore, the content distribution can be performed by a parallel multi-source download scheme to allow peers serving each other.
- **Business and revenue model:** in a standard music store like the iTunes market place, a big reseller sells the content to a wide population of users that pay for the service (the item itself and the distribution of it). In this case, the customer does not gain the right to redistribute the content. She can only consume it according to the license conditions. The Peer-to-Peer scenario introduces new aspects that the business and the revenue models have to deal with. Together with the typical merchants, e.g. a record company, the scenario is populated by a set of peers that contribute to the system: they buy, sell and distribute the content in a collaborative manner. Moreover, each peer can play different roles at the same time. This use case tries to introduce new economic models that enable profit-sharing and fairness amongst peers.

Starting from the definition of the types of users introduced above, we identify the following actors:

1. A Content Item f .
2. A License related to f , packaged in a DCI file and signed by a License Provider Device (LPD).
3. The Creator of a Content Item f , that deposits all the information about f . It can be the author of f , or who owns the copyright of f (e.g., a record company).
4. The Distribution Right is issued/delegated by the Creator when she authorizes a peer to further distribute a given content.
5. The Distributor is a regular peer that has gained the distribution right for a given f . Usually, a peer is authorized to distribute f immediately after he received it.
6. The End-User is a peer that buys and downloads an object f directly from the Creator or via an authorized Distributor.

Usually, in an economic transaction, fairness means that all the participants have to be remunerated for the performed actions. As previously described, in a Peer-to-Peer system the users share not only digital contents, but also hardware resources like computational power or bandwidth. The system intends to remunerate a peer both for the original content she shared as well as for the physical resources provided. Accordingly, the main idea is that when a peer downloads a Content Item, then it should pay both the creator

and the distributor.

We can assume that each Content Item f has two costs:

- an ownership cost $C_a(f)$
- a distribution cost $C_d(f)$

Hence, the total cost of f is $C(f) = C_a(f) + C_d(f)$, which is exactly the price that the user should pay for gaining it. For example, a MP3 song s can have a cost of \$1, where $C_a(s) = \$0.99$ and $C_d(s) = \$0.01$; a DIVX movie m , can costs \$6, where $C_a(m) = \$5.50$ and $C_d(s) = \$0.50$.

Anyway, we will assume that $C_a(f)$ and $C_d(f)$ are always deducible from the meta information contained in the DCI segment.

The costs for the distribution and the ownership of a given object are substantially different. They depend on several criteria, most of them based on the market trends. With respect to the distribution model, we have three scenarios:

1. the distributor is the creator (or a delegate),
2. there is only one distributor,
3. there are multiple distributors, i.e., multi-source download

Figure 2-1 summarizes the actors and the messages involved in the previous three scenarios.

When the Creator of a resource creates a Content Item and, therefore, the License associated, he has to define the revenue policies in order to set the ownership and distribution costs. There are many feasible scenarios that strongly depend on the terms of the License. In the following, we describe two possible schemes:

1. The Content Item f is unprotected and freely distributed for non-commercial purposes. In this case, both the $C_a(f)$ and $C_d(f)$ costs can be null.
2. The Content Item f is protected by a Commercial License. The Creator defines $C_a(f)$ and $C_d(f)$ according to the pricing mechanism implemented in the market. When a Receiver buys the item f , she has to pay $C_a(f)$ to the Creator and $C_d(f)$ to the peers that participate to the distribution process. Afterwards, the Receiver acquires the Distribution Right and she becomes a licensed distributor for f .

The dynamics described above is strongly related to the notion of incentives to cooperate and, in particular, with the countermeasures adopted to fight the free-riding phenomenon.

In fact, the market tends to attain a scenario in which peers have not the tendency to deviate from a cooperative behavior in which they trade digital contents and physical resources, because it represents the most profitable strategy.

In order for a market to take place, we will assume the presence of mechanisms for accounting services and resources consumption as well as functions for crediting and debiting users.

We assume the existence of a function $pay(id_X, id_Y, v)$ that invokes all the measures in order to securely provide a payment of value v from user X to user Y . The use case is not related to a particular scheme, anyway, the iPay [77] specification can provide all the necessary functionalities.

Figure 2-1. Actors and the messages involved in the FairP2PMarketPlace scenario

2.2 Requirements

2.2.1 System overview

The system has to fully support an interoperable Digital Right Management System. In this way we have to take into account the guidelines and specifications provided by DMP [78], [79], [80], [81], [75], [75].

Figure 2-2 shows the value chain in a interoperable DRM. There are for main boxes representing the responsibilities as Distributed Services, Content Creation, Content Providing, Stationary Audio/Video. In these boxes we can imagine the relative Devices running the roles written in the ellipses.

The Service Provider Devices are transversal to the others as they can be addressed in every ring of the chain.

In our Peer-to-Peer infrastructure, the main difference with respect to the standard client-server architecture, resides in the content provider as it is distributed and mirrored and can also provide a partial content in the multi source download scenario.

Figure 2-2. Value Chain of iDRM

2.2.2 Expected operational environment system constraint and performance

Concerning the environment, our aim is to address several and different Operating Systems and Platforms. This is the same goal as Chillout [82]. Our implementation has to maintain the multiplatform capability. The hardware commonly available for a laptop must be sufficient for running the iDRM Peer-to-Peer solution. We can figure out that the memory needed should not exceed one Gbyte and the computing power needed should not require more than a simple CPU.

The bandwidth provided by an ADSL connectivity should be enough for running the solution, even if the intrinsic asymmetric connection cannot give good performances in an infrastructure where peers, by definition, are actually client and server at the same time, hence they communicate symmetrically.

2.2.3 High level diagram of the system

Figure 2-3 shows the main components identified for having an iDRM System.

Figure 2-3. Devices involved in the iDRM system

The yellow boxes provide transversal services to all the involved devices and they should be centralized services. They are responsible for identifying devices, contents and domains. In the following we do not take into account the last, as the domains in a Peer-to-Peer topology can be figured out as Overlays and need a special analysis, which is beyond the scope of this paper.

The rose boxes are actually the end users and the only difference in our network topology is that these SAV have to be able to access contents from several distributed providers. Anyway these content providers, represented by the green coloured box in the middle, are essentially different from the standard architecture. In a Peer-to-Peer environment the Content Provider has to deal with the specific topology and in our DHT case it has to publish the hashed metadata of the Contents to the network.

Also it has to provide the Access to the content to the other Content Providers by means of standard protocols based on TCP/IP. In the following we summarise the requirements into 3 main categories: network infrastructure, device and content.

2.2.4 Requirements on network infrastructure

In order to have a complete iDRM System on a Peer-to-Peer infrastructure, we have to find out the most powerful Peer-to-Peer solution that should be able to realise the use cases discussed above, as well as all the requirements and prerequisites coming from the interoperability of the DRM System.

Moreover, focusing the attention to the Peer-to-Peer network infrastructure, the chosen solution must satisfy the following requirements:

1. It has to be immediately available
2. It has to be stable
3. It has to be provided by some kind of Open Source license
4. It has to be easily integrable into the Chillout Platform [82]
5. It has to be a structured Peer-to-Peer System based on DHT (Distributed Hash Table) topologies because:
 - (a) it solves some limitations and constraints due to the unstructured Peer-to-Peer System of second generation as scalability, performance, limited number of hop per search.
 - (b) it has to enable the scientific experimentation of the solution, combined together with an iDRM System, in order to involve researchers and universities.
 - (c) it has to be open to new features/technologies as capable of taking into account Social/Semantic/... Overlay Networks (SON) [83] and also value added services as recommendation systems.
6. It has to support metadata queries on all the published contents available on the network as well as on a specific peer. The queries should be as follows:
 - (a) simple keyword queries
 - (b) structured queries as hierarchy and range queries

- (c) queries for similarity searches on contents [84] as well as rights [85], [86]
- 7. It has to support a schema for metadata management as follows:
 - (a) describing the content itself (multimedia features) MPEG-7 [87]
 - (b) describing social and semantic information MPEG-7
 - (c) expressing the license MPEG-21 REL [88]
- 8. It has to enable peers to share and protect their own real identity.
- 9. It has to support the use of a virtual identity of the user.
- 10. It has to support the dynamic discovery of the distributed services available on the network [89]
- 11. It has to be able to monitor the content transfer between peers.
- 12. It has to enable peers to load/store their contents with the following modalities:
 - contents loaded/stored onto the own shared directory
 - contents loaded/stored onto the shared directory of an agreeing peer
- 13. It has to support several and different business models
- 14. It has to support the multi-source transport/download from peers having the whole as well as partial content as source.

2.2.5 Requirements on devices

In our environment a Peer-to-Peer Device could act as a Content Provider Device (CPD), a Content Creation Device (CCD), a Stationary Audio/Video Device (SAV), or a combination of them: it is important to notice that all these logical components can be bundled into the same software package and therefore can run on the same hardware device, hence on the same peer.

A peer running as simple SAV Device could actually apply for a free ride as it only consume contents and resources, without supplying the network with it own resources (that's done by CPD). As we are facing the distribution of Governed Contents we have to address this problem. In our scenario, the free riding as we know it is not possible at all. The user can copy/share whatever he wants and can provide files unprotected and not governed by any license, but the system will not take into account these items and nobody will be able neither to look for nor to access them.

Wrapping up, a peer can act as SAV, consuming the items (perhaps paying for accessing them), as well as CPD, providing contents and in the FairP2PMarketPlace scenario he should be able to have revenues for this feature. Lastly a peer can act as CCD, creating the contents and publishing them on the network infrastructure.

We have to point out that the CCD has to be bundled with the CPD because once the content is created it has to be published and made available by means of the content provider. We are willing to disable the publication of a content item on a different peer than the creator. In the future a different configuration could

be possible, where a peer can actually run only the Creation Device, but a more in-depth analysis should be done especially concerning the security, bandwidth consumption, and fake uses.

The SAV device represents the End-User Device, able to apply for a search on the peered network and consume the items found, according to their licence rights and constraints.

2.2.5.1 Requirements on user-devices

As stated above, in our scenario, the User-Device will embed the following functionalities:

1. Content Provider Device (CPD)
2. Content Creation Device (CCD)
3. Stationary Audio/Video Device (SAV)

Considering these 3 components (CPD, CCD, SAV) available on the User-Device acting as peer, we can better define the responsibilities.

The **CPD** has to be able to:

1. Join the Peer-to-Peer network,
2. Apply for a put(key,value) into the network, indexing the contents in the chosen topology
3. Support the multi source download, by means of appropriated API

The **CCD** has to able to:

1. Join the Peer-to-Peer network
2. Ask for a License to the License Provider Device
3. Access the DRM Tool Provider Device
4. Create the DCI/DCF structure to be published on the network
5. Push the created content to the related Content Provider Device (running on the same peer)

The **SAV** has to be able to:

1. Join the Peer-to-Peer network,
2. Apply for a get(key) on the network, searching for some content, where key should be a keyword as well as a structured query
3. Use content according to its License
4. Access License from LPD (internal as well as external to the Peer-to-Peer network)

2.2.6 Requirements on contents

Concerning the contents, our solution of iDRM on Peer-to-Peer System has to deal with Digital Items, starting from audio and still images files, leaving the video as well as the streaming capabilities for a further analysis.

The metadata referring the digital contents has to be formatted as MPEG-7 [87] and MPEG-21 [89]. The first will take into account metadata concerning the content itself, multimedia features as well as semantic information. The latter has to represent the metadata concerning the expression of the associated Rights.

Our solution has to manage governed content (with an associated License) that could be provided in a clear representation or could be protected by means of DRM Tools

Each Content Item shall contain at least:

- Content Identifier
- Content Metadata
- License(s)
- Resources (inline or referenced)

and optionally:

- DRM Information
- DRM Tools
- Event Report Request

The structures of the mentioned DCI and DCF files are represented in figure 2-4 and figure 2-5.

These files represent our governed content (DCF). Even if a peer can share several items also unprotected as well as ungoverned, the CPD will not provide them to the other peers and the related metadata will not be indexed on the network.

Hence we can assume that in our solution we only deal with governed content. Other scenarios are also possible but are left for further analysis.

Taking into account only Governed Items means that our solution prevents unauthorized copies and, even if a peer acting a Content Provider is able to store and share several items coming from different peers, he can access only those he holds the rights for.

Figure 2-4. Structure of DCF file

Figure 2-5. Structure of DCI file

2.3 Specifications

2.3.1 Architecture overview and preliminary design

According to the requirements state above and the Devices [90] that the iDRM System has to deal with, in the following we describe the architecture overview, highlighting the logical components together with their dependencies and responsibilities. A peer has to supply the functionalities of three main Devices: CPD, SAV, CCD.

The deployment diagram shown in Figure 2-6 has been realized according to UML [91] guidelines: physical nodes are represented by cubes, components are represented by a rectangle with two little boxes on the left hand side, dependencies are represented as dashed arrows and stereotypes (custom types for our needs) are depicted with double angular brackets. The Peer-to-Peer network infrastructure is coloured in violet. In

the top left a Peer acting both as CCD and CPD is shown. The CCD creates the DCF file, asking for a License to the LPD as well as for a DRMTool to the DRMTool-PD. Hence CCD publishes the created DCF by means of the CPD. Also it has to publish the key-value pair to the DHT where the value is the Content (or the reference to it, or other redirecting topologies) and the key is the SHA of the Content (or other methodologies).

Figure 2-6. Overview of the proposed architecture overview for iDRM on a Peer-to-Peer System

At the bottom we have described two possible configurations: on the left there is a peer acting exclusively as CPD, simply providing access to contents furnished by the peer itself or previously purchased. It is also able to look for Contents querying the DHT. On the right there is a peer acting simply as SAV that has to look for metadata and has to access to the LPD and to the DRMTool-PD in the case that the content is governed and also protected.

The SAV component will access contents provided by CPD remotely or locally, as shown in the middle, where the peer runs both SAV and CPD logical component.

The DHT infrastructure in the middle represents the indexing layer. It should be considered as the logical space of the topology even if we can consider the whole peered network as made up of all the components coloured in violet. The communication between the CPDs takes place on TCP/IP and could be available on different standard protocols. At least CPD must exchange files by means of socket communication.

Anyway, it should be recognized that the DHT topology acts as a distributed index, enabling the user to discover the CPD that stores some specific content. Once the user has identified the searched resource, he will access it directly joining the CPD. Also the CPDs can share the same governed content and that's the reason why there is a direct connection between them in Figure 2-6

2.3.2 Metadata representation and indexing

We analyze the metadata to be taken into account and to be indexed, the query format to be used for querying the system and the content access and distribution, since there could be several CPDs having the same resources as well as partial contents distributed on peers.

Dealing with multimedia items implies that we have to represent the metadata describing the item itself (referred to as multimedia features in the following) and the metadata expressing the related License.

We adopt MPEG-7 [87] for describing multimedia features such as text, colours, keyframes, temporal decomposition, semantic information, etc.... In particular we make use of the MPEG-7 Simple Metadata Profile [92], which is a meaningful subset of MPEG-7 to be used for indexing purposes, when we can identify a limited number of fields to be indexed in the DHT.

We adopt MPEG-21 [89] for expressing all the licenses to be managed by our system. MPEG-21 REL [88] provides three main Profiles:

1. Open Release Content (ORC),
2. Mobile And optical Media (MAM),
3. Dissemination And Capture (DAC) which can be used to extract a subset of meaningful fields to index Licenses.

The following main fields are present in a License expressed by MPEG-21 REL: Issuer, Principal, Right, Condition and Resource.

For Licenses as well as Multimedia Features, we have to find out the appropriate fields and the schema to be indexed in the DHT, in order to be able to supply structured queries.

Indexing of the Contents will be performed in two distinct phases:

1. a first phase for indexing all the available metadata expressed as MPEG-7 and MPEG-21, with standard methodologies as XML-DBMS
2. a second phase working on a metadata subset concerning multimedia features and rights, stored into the DHT.

This approach gives the best compromise between the two opposite solutions:

1. indexing all metadata on the DHT
2. indexing only a few keywords.

The former solution is highly resource consuming and has a very low efficiency. The latter doesn't allow for structured queries as required by *P2P iDRM* requisites [73]

In the following we focus on the best indexing strategy enabling structured queries in an efficient way on DHT topologies.

First of all we are suggesting to make use of the MPEG-7 Simple Metadata Profile [92], with the User and Core Description Profile as the minimum information set for expressing the metadata related to the multimedia content itself, whereas for the License we are suggesting to make use only of the following MPEG-21 elements: Issuer, Principal and Right.

We can imagine the indexing process composed of two main tasks: first, once the SHA [21] value has been obtained, the CCD stores the Content (the whole DCF/DCI with all the metadata expressed by means of MPEG-7 and MPEG-21) into the DHT; next, the simple metadata profile, the issuer, the principal and the right are extracted and stored into the DHT, referring to the key obtained before.

A further task could be to store all these information into an XML Database in a centralised service. Also we can store the MPEG-7 files in a separate Overlay as well as the MPEG-21 files. In this way we can have different DHT-based systems for managing different kind of metadata enabling different specific query processor for each overlay.

2.3.3 Metadata retrieval and query format

During the 77th MPEG meeting (Klagenfurt, Austria, July 2006), the MPEG committee released a call for proposal for an MPEG Query Format (MPQF) framework (initially named MPEG-7 Query Format) and specified a set of requirements. In the next months the MPQF (ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG11) will be released and will be possible to implement a specific software for querying the fragments of MPEG-7. Nevertheless there is no Query Format proposed or analysed so far for MPEG-21. Although at the moment we are not able to suggest a complete standard for querying our DCF files, we can exploit the efficiency of the DHT index to divide the query into a chain of Query Processors.

The first processor is responsible for the query user interface and deals with the metadata subset defined in Section 2.3.2, where the MPEG-7 has the Simple Profile elements and the MPEG-21 has the Issuer, Principal and Right elements.

The first processor asks for the metadata subset, querying the DHT, and retrieves a **Result Set**. Hence the flow chain asks to the second processor to refine the **Result Set**, accessing the complete metadata structure end extracting some good representation that can be provided to the user.

As an example, a further processor in the chain of the Query Processors, can apply for an MPQF. Hence this kind of approach enables a future implementation of the MPQF as well as other structured queries.

Summarising, we are suggesting an innovative approach for querying the System.

A first query accessing the DHT index, made up of keywords and simple metadata elements, very close to the *User eXperience* [93] of the most search engines widely available on the web.

A second refinement of the Result Set, extracting more information accessing the Contents referred by the first result set, that enables a structured query on whatever schema. It's only a matter of implementing the specific Query Processor to be added to the Query chain.

2.3.4 Content access and distribution

A first implementation of the System requests at least that the access to the contents should be done by mean of socket communication on standard TCP/IP.

That's the minimal requirement for the CPD.

A further analysis, especially for enabling Internet connections outside the DMZs, could point out that an access by HTTP protocol should be performed. Anyway the latter configuration as well as others (e.g. streaming, big size file download, etc.) are beyond the scope of this dissertation.

2.3.4.1 Content creation

The CCD has to create the resource and the related License, interacting at least with the CID and LPD. Hence the CCD has to create the DCI/DCF files (together with the MPEG-7 and MPET-21).

At this point the CCD can publish the Content to the CPD available on the same peer and can store the metadata/keywords into the DHT index.

2.3.4.2 Searching and consuming

The SAV component enables the user to search for contents providing keywords and the schema discussed in Section 3.3, with MPEG-7 Simple Metadata Profile and MPEG-21 Issuer, Principal and Right.

Hence the SAV queries the DHT retrieving the first Result Set and runs the Query Processor Chain in order to refine the Set, providing a detailed result list to the user.

Once the user chooses an item in the Result List, he can access directly the CPD providing the DCF.

In the case that the SAV is running on a peer acting also as CPD, the SAV can ask its CPD to retrieve the Content for a redistribution scope, and then can access the searched content locally.

2.4 Analysis of candidate solutions

2.4.1 Proposed solution

Nowadays the following structured Peer-to-Peer Systems satisfying the requirements needed are available:

1. Bamboo [94] (OpenDHT [95])
2. FreePastry [96]

Both of them are structured Peer-to-Peer Systems of third generation and are suitable for future research as well as for experimenting innovative models.

2.4.1.1 Bamboo

Bamboo can be seen as a re-engineering of the Pastry [13] protocol, with some differences in the geometry. The term geometry is used to refer to the pattern of neighbor links in a DHT, independent of the routing algorithms or neighbor management algorithms used. Bamboo uses the Pastry geometry. It does not, however, use the same joining or neighbor management algorithms. Compared to Pastry, the algorithms are more incremental, a difference that allows Bamboo to better withstand large membership changes in the DHT as well as continuous churn in membership, especially in bandwidth-limited environments. Bamboo is written in an event-driven, single-threaded programming style. In the first place it inherits its structure from SEDA [8], which stands for the Staged, Event-Driven Architecture. As the name suggests, each part of a Bamboo application is a stage; communication is done by passing events to each stage, while the whole application remains single threaded and serialized.

2.4.1.2 FreePastry

FreePastry [96] is a open source (BSD like), modular, Java implementation of the Pastry overlay, intended for deployment on the Internet. The initial release of FreePastry is intended primarily as a tool that allows interested parties to evaluate Pastry, to perform further research and development in Peer-to-Peer substrates, and as a platform for the development of applications. The current release has a lot of performance features including a much more compact serialization than Java Serialization. FreePastry comes with a discrete event simulator that has been optimized and can support 10K-100K nodes on a beefy machine. NAT support is currently limited to users who can set up port forwarding, or have UPnP, but some of the FreePastry community users are investigating integration STUN to expand this capability.

2.4.1.3 Comparison

Both systems are available via sources and/or binary distribution, and, as the support community is big and active, the projects can improve and add new features in the next months.

Table 2-1 shows a quick comparison of the two systems, pointing out the main features.

2.4.2 Selected solution

It is worthwhile to underline that, whatever non commercial solution was adopted, it would necessarily require some bug fixing and custom adaptation. As shown in the summary table, both solutions present some pros and cons that have to be considered. Of course, one of the major points of interest of the Bamboo DHT is the presence of an already maintained, open, and available routing infrastructure: OpenDHT [95], the public deployment of Bamboo [94], runs 24/7 on PlanetLab [97] and is available for testing purposes. However, as long as the routing infrastructure has to be integrated ex novo in the Chillout framework [73], the FreePastry distribution has some major features while Bamboo has not. Above all, in the API there is the complete implementation of the layered applications stack based on the Pastry DHT, i.e., a storage

	Bamboo	Freepastry
Latest Version and Date (2007.12)	2006.03.03	2007.05.17v.2.0_02
Software Distribution	Sources	Sources, Binary (jar)
Language	Java 1.4	Java 5
License	BSD	BSD
Basic functionalities	Routing, Identifier Generation	Routing, Identifier generation
Advanced functionalities	Storage Manager, WebInterface, Data Manager (replication through leaf-set) with a put/get interface	Application Level Multicast management (scribe) archival storage (past), high-bandwidth content distribution (splitstream)
Community	Mailing list: active (2007.08)	Mailing list: active (2007.08)
Documentation	Tutorials, Programmers guide	Tutorials, Diagrams, Wireshark dissector, Protocol Specification
Related Project	OpenDHT (a Bamboo-based DHT running 24/7, with XML-RPC put/get interface)	Past (storage), Scribe (event notification/multicast management), SplitStream (streaming)
Routing Infrastructure	Available (OpenDHT)	Not available
Web site	http://bamboo-dht.org/	http://freepastry.rice.edu/

Table 2-1. Comparison of Bamboo and Freepastry Systems (2007.08)

archival interface [96], a multicast management group framework [98] together with a high-bandwidth content distribution [99].

Our analysis has pointed out that **FreePastry** is the best available Peer-to-Peer System, fitting our needs and covering most of the requirements.

Implementation of Interoperable DRM System on Structured Overlay Networks

Preface: *The work described in this chapter is currently under a conference review*

When the WWW was born, in the early 90's, it was mainly designed for exchanging scientific results based on *text*. The protocol enabling what we know as *internet* is actually based on text [100]. Nowadays the web is mostly used for exchanging multimedia items instead of simple text documents and we can recognize that one of the biggest issue is how to describe them. The growing of the available digital items on the web introduces the need of their descriptions. Even if it is possible to share multimedia items, without descriptions it will be very difficult or impossible to search them. Usually people making use of sharing systems on the web do not provide other data than the digital item and, in most cases, its title. This lack of information determines the growth of unstructured information. We can define metadata as the description of the data. Through metadata it is possible to structure the information and thus, on one side, to enhance and enrich the information related to a content and, on the other, to search and retrieve digital items. It's clear that the more detailed are the metadata, the more complex is the structure on which they are inserted. Moreover, in order to be able to have a common understanding of metadata, it is important to adopt *standards*. In this chapter we are proposing the approach used by a fast growing number of scientific communities: the adoption of MPEG-7 [87] for describing metadata related to the digital items and the MPEG-21 [89] for describing metadata related to the associated rights.

With the use of metadata we can cover the lack of structured information but we have to design a suitable way for storing and searching them. Metadata are usually stored in relational (RDB) or object oriented (OODB) databases, mapped to related tables as well as objects. Since the beginning of year 2000, XML [101] was introduced for structuring data and metadata (examples are the well know eXist [102] as well as the more complex and ruled by a *Tree Algebra* [103] as Timber [104]).

The database approach (R/OODB or XML like) forces a central architecture: the central component (i.e., the database, even if mirrored or replicated on some topology) can become the bottleneck of the communication process during the storing and retrieving phases. The introduction of Peer-to-Peer systems allows the distribution of metadata in an efficient way, avoiding single-point-of-failure and, in case of structured Peer-to-Peer system, guaranteeing the scalability to the system. The price to be payed is the limited functionalities concerning the metadata structure indexable on them: structured Peer-to-Peer systems present a flat space of indexes (except for CAN [14], that is *d*-dimensional); that is, each resource and each node is indexed with a key computed in some way from the same space.

This chapter introduces a suitable way for indexing structured metadata on DHT, with special attention to the metadata representing rights, hence having an MPEG-21 form. We are presenting a distributed application

built on a structured overlay network, tailored to insert structured information on a flat space, enabling a hierarchical indexing scheme like the one in [105].

In the two following sections 3.1 and 3.2, a short overview of **FreePastry** and **Chillout** is presented, because our solution is based upon these software modules for managing the level of DHT and iDRM.

3.1 FreePastry

The conclusions of section 2.4.2 have chosen FreePastry as the base software implementation for managing the DHT.

In this section we are giving a brief description of FreePastry taken from the on-line documentation [96]. Pastry provides the following capabilities. First, each node in the Pastry network has a unique, uniform random identifier (nodeId) in a circular 128-bit identifier space. When presented with a message and a numeric 128-bit key, a Pastry node efficiently routes the message to the node with a nodeId that is numerically closest to the key, among all currently live Pastry nodes. The expected number of forwarding steps in the Pastry overlay network is $O(\log N)$, while the size of the routing table maintained in each Pastry node is only $O(\log N)$ in size (where N is the number of live Pastry nodes in the overlay network). At each Pastry node along the route that a message takes, the application is notified and may perform application-specific computations related to the message.

Second, each Pastry node keeps track of its L immediate neighbors in the nodeId space (called the leaf set), and notifies applications of new node arrivals, node failures and node recoveries within the leaf set. Third, Pastry takes into account locality (proximity) in the underlying Internet; it seeks to minimize the distance messages travel, according to a scalar proximity metric like the ping delay. Pastry is completely decentralized, scalable, and self-organizing; it automatically adapts to the arrival, departure and failure of nodes. Peer-to-Peer applications built upon Pastry can utilize its capabilities in many ways, including:

- Mapping application objects to Pastry nodes: Application-specific objects are assigned unique, uniform random identifiers (objIds) and mapped to the k , ($k \geq 1$) nodes with nodeIds numerically closest to the objId. The number k reflects the application's desired degree of replication for the object.
- Inserting objects: Application-specific objects can be inserted by routing a Pastry message, using the objId as the key. When the message reaches a node with one of the k closest nodeIds to the objId, that node replicates the object among the other $k-1$ nodes with closest nodeIds (which are, by definition, in the same leaf set for $k \leq \frac{L}{2}$).
- Accessing objects: Application-specific objects can be looked up, contacted, or retrieved by routing a Pastry message, using the objId as the key. By definition, the message is guaranteed to reach a node that maintains a replica of the requested object unless all k nodes with nodeIds closest to the objId have failed.
- Availability and persistence: Applications interested in availability and persistence of application-specific objects maintain the following invariant as nodes join, fail and recover: object replicas are maintained on the k nodes with numerically closest nodeIds to the objId, for $k > 1$. The fact that

Pastry maintains leaf sets and notifies applications of changes in the set's membership simplifies the task of maintaining this invariant.

- **Diversity:** The assignment of nodeIds is randomly distributed and cannot be corrupted by an attacker. Thus, with high probability, nodes with adjacent nodeIds are diverse in geographic location, ownership, jurisdiction, network attachment, etc. Therefore, the probability that such a set of nodes is conspiring or suffers from correlated failures is low even for modest set sizes. This minimizes the probability of a simultaneous failure of all k nodes that maintain an object replica. Likewise, quorum-based protocols can be used to securely update and query the state of replicated objects, despite the presence of a limited number of malicious nodes in the system.
- **Load balancing:** Both nodeIds and objIds are randomly assigned and uniformly distributed in the 128-bit Pastry identifier space. Without requiring any global coordination, this results in a good first-order balance of storage requirements and query load among the Pastry nodes, as well as network load in the underlying Internet.
- **Object caching:** Applications can cache objects on the Pastry nodes encountered along the paths taken by insert and lookup messages. Pastry's network locality properties make it likely that messages routed with the same key from nearby nodes converge early, thus lookups are likely to intercept nearby cached objects. This distributed caching offloads the k nodes that hold the primary replicas of an object, and it minimizes client delays and network traffic by dynamically caching copies near interested clients.
- **Efficient, scalable information dissemination:** Applications can perform efficient multicast using reverse path forwarding along the tree formed by the routes from clients to the node with nodeId numerically closest to a given objId. Pastry's network locality properties ensure that the resulting multicast trees are efficient; i.e., they result in efficient data delivery and resource usage in the underlying Internet.

In our implementation we are making use of **Freepastry** 2.0.02 and in the following we are describing the basic functionalities (taken from the online tutorial). Actually we are dealing with *Past* the large-scale, peer-to-peer archival storage facility, which is the FreePastry's DHT.

It has insert() and lookup() operations, the basic operations for managing the DHT. In Freepastry, as well as in other DHT implementations, these operations have to deal with the network topology and the related latency. Hence *Past* has introduced a new concept, the **Continuation**, in order to insert and lookup keys in an asynchronous way. A continuation is similar to a callback, or in java, a Listener, but it is typically used only once. A google search for continuations will show you a variety of uses in computer science, but the primary use for them in FreePastry is to handle network latency, or other types of IO that may block or take a significant amount of time.

To understand why we use continuations, let's look at an alternative style of calls. RMI/RPC style calls are generally blocking calls. Blocking calls work similar to a regular function call. The lookup command in *Past* could look like:

```
public Result lookup(Id id) {  
    // blocking network call
```

}
 But if the network call takes a while to execute due to latency, then your program will block until it completes. In the meantime you could be doing other lookups, but because of this style of call, you are forced to wait, or use a lot of threads. Continuations allow you to "continue" processing when the result arrives, and in the meantime issue other requests. Let's look at the `rice.Continuation` interface

```
public interface Continuation {
/**
 * Called when a previously requested result is now available.
 * @param result The result of the command.
 */
public void receiveResult(Object result);

/**
 * Called when an exception occurred as a result of the previous command.
 * @param result The exception which was caused.
 */
public void receiveException(Exception result);
}
```

With the *Continuation*, in Past the code to do a lookup looks like this:

```
public void lookup(Id id, Continuation command) {
// non-blocking network call
}
```

Note the differences between this call and the alternative approach mentioned before:

- The method takes a *Continuation*.
- There is no return value.

When the result arrives, Past will call `command.receiveResult()` with the response. Inside the continuation, you can complete the task that required the lookup. If instead, an error occurs, Past will call `command.receiveException()`. Note that because `receiveResult()` is called with an `Object`, you must cast the result to what you are expecting from the lookup.

In the next sections we will present the use of a *Generic Continuation*, in order to take into account whatever object we have to deal with. This is a *Template* programming pattern, widely used especially in C++ and introduced in Java in the JDK1.5.

We have used Freepastry, taking special care to have explicit dependencies to a common layer of API, instead of binding the application to a specific release. Rice University has provided the commonAPI layer, with a `CommonAPI.Universal` interface to structured overlays.

The `rice.p2p.commonapi` package provides an interface similar to the one provided in [106]. The API is

designed to allow applications to be written in a protocol-independent manner, allowing the easy migration of applications from Pastry to Chord to CAN to Tapestry, etc....

Applications need only interact with the interfaces in the *rice.p2p.commonapi* package, and need not worry about anything in the *rice.pastry* packages. That's what we have followed as it will be shown later.

Another important concept that we have to introduce is the *Application* as we are going to show a specific implementation.

An Application is defined as a program that runs on a Node. This is an interface which all applications on top of a Node must export. This interface allows the underlying node to deliver message, inform the application of passing messages, and changes in the neighbor nodes. You can have multiple Applications on a single node, and you can even have multiple instances of an Application on the same node. Why would you want multiple instances on the same node? Many applications in FreePastry are intermediate applications that provide a service for higher level applications. It is convenient to have a separate instances of say... Scribe for each higher application that would like to multicast. This way you know that any messages that scribe delivers are in regards to your higher level traffic, and you don't need to distinguish that traffic between multiple high level applications.

3.2 Chillout

Chillout [82] is the name given to the reference software implementation of the Digital Media Project (DMP)[90]. DMP is a no profit organization that has recently approved a version 3.0 of its specification, called Interoperable DRM Platform (IDP-3.0). Chillout is also the reference implementation of ISO/IEC 23000-5 Media Streaming Application Format [107], targeting the distribution of governed content over streaming channels.

In July 2006 a group of DMP members submitted a proposal to MPEG to standardise a Media Streaming Multimedia Application Format (MS MAF) based on DMP IDP specification, which has reached in October 2007 the stage of Final Draft International Standard. For this reason, Chillout is also the reference implementation of ISO/IEC 23000-5 Media Streaming Application Format [107], targeting the distribution of governed content over streaming channels.

Chillout is released as Open Source Software (OSS) under the Mozilla Public Licence v.1.1. and its composed by several layers:

- a Core Layer,
- a normative library providing the functionalities to generate and parse
 1. the XML structure defined by IDP
 2. files and streams for transport across devices
 3. messages exchanged by two devices performing DMP protocols
- an Auxiliary Layer and an Application Layer that provide a number of applications to create, distribute and access content and associated information

Chillout can virtually handle any type of audio-visual resource, and allows creating content with inline or referenced resources and metadata describing them. Specific profiles of TV-Anytime [108] and MPEG-7 [87] are the native choices of metadata schemes for describing some characteristics of the content. On the other hand, MPEG-21 REL is the technology of choice for representing the IPR information related to content and parts thereof. Chillout can handle both content only governed by a license (a Creative Commons-like approach) and at the same time content governed by a license and also protected by encryption techniques, thus enabling a broad variety of application scenarios and business models.

The most important technologies adopted by Chillout are:

1. A data structure capable of hosting diverse data types accompanying a resource audio, video, image, text etc. (Digital Item Declaration or DID [109])
2. An identification system of content (Digital Identification or DII [110])
3. A set of technologies usable to protect content (Intellectual Property Management and Protection or IPMP [111])
4. A language to express rights associated to a resource (Rights Expression Language or REL [112, 113, 114])
5. A file format for storing Digital Items and resources (File Format [111])
6. A technology to transmit Digital Items in streaming mode (Digital Item Streaming or DIS [115])

3.3 Indexing and Retrieving Rights Metadata

In the proposed scenario, a digital resource r is associated to a wide range of metadata, spanning from MPEG-7 multimedia content descriptions to MPEG-21 rights management. To lighten the load of each node, we do not index all the MPEG-7 and MPEG-21 metadata: we chose a subset of the overall tags. This subset is indexed and used for a first step of the query process. To refine the result set it is possible to query locally the retrieved resources against the complete schemas through well-established approaches. This hybrid strategy can lead to a good trade-off between efficiency, scalability and query expressiveness. Given the resource r and the selected subset of metadata $M_r = \{m_0, m_1, \dots, m_i\}$, we computed the set of identifiers $I_{M_r} = \{id_{m_0}, id_{m_1}, \dots, id_{m_i}\}$. Each one of these identifiers must reference r itself, in order to allow metadata based queries. In other words, we insert on the DHT a set of pair $\langle key, value \rangle$ in the form $\langle id_{m_i}, r \rangle, \forall id_{m_i} \in I_{M_r}$.

The problem we are facing here comes from the flat identifier space of most of DHTs: the structured nature of metadata (e.g., a XML-based representation) must be mapped in a flat set of $\langle key, value \rangle$ pairs.

To solve this problem, we propose a hierarchical indexing scheme. The first operation is to gather the keywords for the content that we want to index. First of all we can divide contents between governed and non-governed. The former do not have licenses associated and the keywords to be indexed are just the (MPEG-7 elements) name, author and resource description (e.g., size, creation date, and so on). The latter

has a license and we have defined the following structure to be indexed: for each right described in the license we index the three (MPEG-21 elements) values: **issuer**, **grant**, **principal** (see Figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1. *Simplified model of MPEG-21 REL*

After building the resource r and calculating its identifier (i.e., id_r), for each one of these metadata, a key is calculated, respectively id_i , id_g , id_p , and inserted on the storage layer of the DHT, associated with the reference to the resource. In order to allow more complex queries, we inserted on the DHT several mappings for each resource. First, we inserted the issuer, the grant and the principal (as well as typical MPEG-7 tags, e.g., title and author).

$$\langle id_i, id_r \rangle ; \langle id_g, id_r \rangle ; \langle id_p, id_r \rangle$$

Furthermore, we inserted all possible combination of those three right metadata. What we did was combining the previously calculating identifiers and combine them to achieve the following mappings:

$$\langle (id_i, id_g), id_r \rangle$$

$$\langle (id_g, id_p), id_r \rangle$$

$$\langle (id_i, id_g, id_p), id_r \rangle$$

It's clear, at this point, that several identifiers point to the same resource, that is, a user can search for “all the digital items issued by someone”, or “all the media that has a grant of *copy*”, beyond looking for titles and authors. Since the identifiers in I_{M_r} are built from MPEG-21 tags, it's easy to combine them in order to build those *complex* identifiers.

We are indexing rights metadata on a structured overlay network, allowing users to search governed resources looking for specific issuers, grants or principals. A user querying the DHT for a resource can start looking for a specific issuer: the returned result set will be the set of all the resources inserted by this issuer (if any). Our scheme allows more specific queries, simply combining previous identifiers and computing the new *complex* ones.

3.4 Application implementation

In order to fit the requirements presented in Chapter 2 (and especially in Section 2.3.1) the following Figure 3-2 shows a simplified schema of the *Chillout devices* involved in the application implementation. The Peer-to-Peer network is the central point connecting together the creator (CCD), the player (SAV) and the provider (CPD).

Figure 3-2. *Chillout devices involved in the implementation*

Other connections are available and are not shown for simplicity.

According to Chillout reference implementation, we are making use of two main file format for managing contents: the DCI (DMP Content Information) and the DCF (the DMP Content File).

The DMP Content Information (DCI) is used for specifying the metadata, the rights information (the modalities according to which other users will be able to use the resource) and if necessary the protection information for the resource. The DMP Content File (DCF) is the wrapper of the DCI and also the resources described by the DCI. DCF can have the resources within the file or can refer to them by means of pointers. The work described deals with these two kind of files and all the metadata are kept inside the DCFs. We have parsers/writers for reading and storing metadata by DCF and this is the key element in our architecture because we are indexing a meaningful subset of the metadata available in the DCF and indexing the DCF as well. The user will be able to search for the subset and at the same time, by means of a MetadataService protocol, can access the entire DCF in a completely distributed way.

Figure 3-3 points out the dependencies between the Chillout software components and shows the three main components implemented described later.

The reader can recognize that a good refactoring of the software components realizing the CCD, SAV and CPD has isolated a core Chillout component, useful for all the Devices. Following the same guideline we have implemented the Peer-to-Peer component depending only to the core component, which will be the core library of Chillout development.

Figure 3-3. Dependencies between the Peer-to-Peer software component and the other Chillout devices

We can figure out the implementation as made up of three layers: the DHT, the Transport and the Application layer well shown in Figure 3-4. The **DHT Layer** is responsible for managing the structured overlay network and after a survey of the available solutions we have opted for making use of FreePastry [96] as underlying software.

The separation level between the FreePastry implementation and our application is the package `rice.p2p.commonapi` realizing the *Facade pattern* which is a bundle of interfaces commonly used by several DHT implementation. This choice leaves us the possibility of having another overlay implementation in the future, as Chord [12] or Mchord [116] as well as Kademia [117], etc.

In order to communicate to the DHT layer we have implemented the *Continuations* for insert and lookup operations. The shown *ChilloutContinuation* component is responsible for receiving results from the DHT. The *ChilloutContinuation* realize a *Command pattern* where the command is the method *receiveResults* (and *receiveExceptions*), which is called when a *lookup* operation has been performed. We have used a *CollectorParameter* pattern in order to collect results from the continuations. The main reason is that the Continuation works asynchronously because it has to take into account the network latency and topology reconfiguration due to the peers joining and leaving the overlay. Above the DHT Layer we have the **Transport Layer**, with two components: one is responsible for transferring the resources (multimedia files) and the other is responsible for transferring the related metadata, actually a java object which wraps the the DCF [118] file.

In this way we are able to ask to a specific peer the information related to a certain resource that it owns.

Figure 3-4. High level component diagram of the presented application

In figure 3-4 we have pointed out the sockets, according to UML 2.0 specifications [119], for underlining the server sockets listening inside the components.

The upper layer of the figure is the **Application Layer**, which is responsible for managing the entire application and has an explicit dependency to the *ChilloutCore* [82] package.

This layer makes use of a DCI and DCF wrapper, extended from the Chillout implementation, in order to parse the Digital Content files. The structures of DCI and DCF are shown in Figures 2-5 2-4. We can imagine the DCF file as a container of the DCI and the resources as well and the DCI file as made up of the descriptions of the contents and the related licenses. The content are described with MPEG-7 elements and the license with MPEG-21 elements.

Hence, the parser is able to provide all the information needed by the application level.

The main approach is the following. Chillout reference software is responsible for creating the DCI and DCF files. Actually there is a specific device, the **Content Creation Device** [120] which is able to create both files structures, given one or more resources to be governed. Once the DCF (or simple DCI) is created, we have to share it on the Structured Peer-to-Peer network.

We have implemented a DCF wrapper and according to some rules we create the indexes of the content and store them into the DHT. We are making use of the DHT only for storing index and not the contents. The rules for indexing are very simple as we do not want to provide an exhaustive representation of the content

as DHT index. The first operation is to gather the keywords for the content that we want to index. First of we can divide contents between governed and non-governed. The former do not have licenses associated and the keywords to be indexed are only the name, the author, the resource description as size, creation date. The latter has a license and we have defined the following structure to be indexed. For each right described in the license we index the three values: **issuer grant principal**. For every grant we index the bundle of issuer, grant, principal (with the several permutations), pointing to the associated DCF file. Hence in the DHT we have the indexes of the general purpose metadata and in addition for governed resources, we have the bundle of grants pointing to the content.

We are using the DHT only for indexing purpose and not for storing the contents. The peer which is responsible for a specific range of indexes could not have the related contents. In order to ensure the consistency of the system, we have implemented the *persistence layer* of the DHT, managing directly the storage of the indexes in the peer environment. Also, we have defined a persistence management of the contents as well.

The lookup operation on the DHT could be done by simple keywords or structured bundle of issuer- grant-principal. The result at low level is the index of the Content whose DCF (DCI) is fulfilling the request.

The application layer contacts the sources (the peers publishing the contents) asking for more information on the content. The DCFMetadataService component communicates on a separate channel, by means of a specific protocol which is able to exchange the wrapper of the DCF. In this way we can provide to the user all the available information related to the searched keywords and grants.

The results of the query are collected by means of the Collecting parameters component, in our case the CollectorResults, which has a Thread looking for the asynchronous return messages provided by the continuation.

Figure 3-5. Class Diagram of the DHT Layer

The user can select the specific content from the result list and the application layer will contact the specific source (couple of internet address and port) owning the Content.

This is done making use of the FileTransportation component which communicate in another separate channel, with a specific protocol for exchanging files.

Our first approach was a simple file transportation but we are looking for making use of more sophisticated solutions enabling the multi-source download, as Bit-Torrent [6] exchange protocol or other as GridFTP [121] running well exchanging files with size larger than 2Giga-Byte.

The Class Diagram of Figure 3-5 shows the low level implementation of the DHT layer, specifically the classes responsible for coupling Freepastry. We have defined a *Facade pattern* class, the CoreLayer, used by the CoreApplication class, which could be identified as the most important element interacting between the DHT and the Application layers.

As the reader can recognize, we have limited the dependencies of the Application classes to the common rice.p2p.commonapi package, in order to be able to handle different DHT implementations in the future.

In order to be able to manage different Contents, we have created a *generic* implementation (*Template Class*) of the exchanged content, named ChilloutContent. In our context it is responsible for managing DCI wrappers, but in the future we can have several object adaptations.

3.5 Application User eXperience

In this section we present the application functionalities that the user can experience for joining the network, publish a governed content and search for digital items providing some metadata. A list of Figures follows in order to show a typical logical flow that a user can play. In Figure 3-6 the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the Chillout Stationary Audio Visual (SAV) Device is shown, which allows the user to browse and play digital **contents**. In addition a new menu *Peer-to-Peer* has been added, that allows the user to set up the peered topology and join/leave the network as well as publish and search for contents.

The full list of implemented functionalities of the *Peer-to-Peer* menu are shown in Figure 3-7 where the user can:

- configure the **Overlay Settings** as explained in Figure 3-8
- **Start/Stop** the application, running a new ring if no-one is ready as well as joining a preexisting one
- **View Downloaded** contents, which are stored in a folder in the user home environment
- perform a **Keywords** or **Complex** Lookup, providing simple text or structured metadata according to the schema presented in section 3.3
- **Get Resource** if the user knows the HASH value of a specific content

Figure 3-6. Stationary Audio Visual Device User Interface with the Peer-to-Peer extension

Figure 3-7. The Peer-to-Peer menu list

The **Overlay Settings** let the user configure the network topology, communication ports, IP Address (as the selected row in Figure 3-8), the folders for storing contents and indexes, number of nodes, the storage size, the logging level, etc... as shown in Figure 3-8.

Parameter	Current Value
user.storage.folder	user_storage
default.replica	0
local.ip	192.168.3.39
default.content.type	dcf
local.port	9091
id.factory.class	rice.pastry.commonapi.PastryIdFactory
application.name	AppPersistent
file.download.folder	download
file.transport.port	10000
file.download.folder.client	download_client
bootstrap.ip	192.168.3.17
bootstrap.port	9091
user.content.list	usercontentsDB.bin
nodes.n	10
storage.size	10485760
pastry.log.level	INFO
file.persistent.folder	keys_storage
file.transport.sync.milliseconds	1000
metadata.service.port	10001

Figure 3-8. Configuration menu: the Overlay Settings

Every time the user wants to change the configuration or start/join a ring, a folder structure is created/updated according to Figure 3-9, where is shown the xml file storing all the Overlay Settings parameters.

Figure 3-9. User Home folder structure of chillout: the P2P folder

When the user starts the application, he can decide to join a running ring or initialize a new one. The choice is done in the Overlay Settings, where the user can define the bootstrap IP Address. If it is the localhost the application has to initialize a new ring, otherwise it has to try to connect the bootstrap peer, joining the running ring. If the connection is not available, a new ring is started locally.

Figure 3-10 shows the output of the FreePastry API logging the joining of a ring.

Once the network is running, the user can search or publish contents. In Figure 3-11 the user can look at the downloaded contents (or previously copied content in the download folder) and he can decide to publish them checking the last column.

This operation forces the application to parse the contents, extract the relevant metadata and create the associated HASH id in order to push them into the DHT ring.

Figure 3-12 shows the operation of put(HASH, metadata) into the ring, where two contents are indexed in the sources identified by address:port - 192.168.3.17:9091.

The complex lookup operation can perform a query based on the fields shown in Figure 3-13:

```

[java] - server socket listening on port 10000
[java] - Metadata service: server socket listening on port 10001
[java] Environment settato di default INFO
[java] :rice.selector@Default:1198757111555:SelectorManager -- Default starting...
[java] 0x0A79C7:rice.selector@<0x0A79C7..> Selector:1198757111580:SelectorManager -- <0x0A79C7..> Selector starting...
[java] 0x0A79C7:rice.pastry.socket:1198757112081:PingManager binding to euwa/192.168.3.39:9091 [-1776243629760582148]
[java] 0x0A79C7:rice.pastry.socket:1198757112591:CHECK DEAD: euwa/192.168.3.39:9091 [-1776243629760582148] CHECKING DEATH OF PATH {192.168.3.17:9091} rto:3000
[java] 0x0A79C7:rice.pastry.standard:1198757112622:ConsistentJonProtocol.setReady()
[java] 0x0A79C7:rice.pastry.standard:1198757112656:PLSP.start(): Setting self as ReadyStrategy
[java] 0x0A79C7:rice.pastry.socket:1198757112656:CHECK DEAD: euwa/192.168.3.39:9091 [-1776243629760582148] CHECKING DEATH OF PATH {192.168.3.17:9091} rto:2280
[java] 0x0A79C7:rice.pastry.socket:1198757112701:PastryNode.notifyReadyObservers(true)
[java] :rice.persistence:1198757112701:Launching persistent storage in /Users/walter/chillout/P2P/keys_storage_192.168.3.39_9091 with name default splitting factor 256
[java] :rice.persistence:1198757112701:Initing directories
[java] :rice.persistence:1198757112702:Initing directory map
[java] :rice.persistence:1198757112702:Initing files
[java] :rice.persistence:1198757112703:Initing file map
[java] :rice.persistence:1198757112703:Syncing metadata
[java] :rice.persistence:1198757112703:Done initing
[java] Environment settato di default INFO
[java] :rice.selector@Default:1198757112706:SelectorManager -- Default starting...
[java] - Id Factory succesful created: rice.pastry.commonapi.PastryIdFactory
[java] - ChilloutP2PManager started

```

Figure 3-10. Starting application: output window of FreePastry

File ID	Title	Type	Dimension [KB]	Licensed	Publish
<0x66706D..>	filippo.dcf	dcf	9,909	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<0x66706D..>	TrailerFrancesco.dcf	dcf	98,006	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Buttons: Publish content, Refresh view, Close

Figure 3-11. Download items view

```

[[<0xF8304B..>]] with destination <0x0A79C7..>
[[<0xF8304B..>]] with destination <0x0A79C7..>
[[Source: /192.168.3.17 9091]] with destination <0x0A79C7..>
[[<0x34075E..>]] with destination <0x0A79C7..>
[[Source: /192.168.3.17 9091]] with destination <0x0A79C7..>

```

Figure 3-12. Digital item publishing: keys management output

- the title, assigned to the content by its creator
- the name of the content creator and/or the name of the resource creator
- the issuer, i.e. the owner of the rights related to the resources
- the grant, which could be play, copy, etc.. A detailed list of grants for some MPEG-21 profiles will be shown in table 4-1
- the principal, i.e. the device which the grant is expressed for

The query is looking for all the contents published on the ring having gallo as creator of contents or resources and play as grant.

Figure 3-13. *Complex lookup menu: looking for all the resources having gallo as creator and play as grant*

The query process could be described in two steps: the first is shown in Figure 3-14 and the second in Figure 3-15.

The first shows the results returned by the DHT index. Hence the application asks the sources having the searched contents by means of the Metadata Service, starting a new thread for each row in the result list. In the first step the user do not know the related metadata as the filename (file name not available), file type, size, and if it is governed with a specific MPEG-21 license. The Metadata Service, provides all the metadata related to the searched contents, getting all the information stored in the DCI files. In this way, the GUI is

Figure 3-14. Complex lookup menu: result view during the Metadata Service: title, dimension,... are asked by the service making use of subtasks running on separated ports

Figure 3-15. Complex lookup menu: result view with all the metadata retrieved by the Metadata Service

updated automatically and the user can see the full list of metadata, which can help the user to choose which content he wants to download.

Checking the last column the user is able to select and download the contents which will be stored in the download folder defined by the user in the Overlay Settings parameters.

Now the user can choose to have a look at its downloaded contents and re-publish the same content.

If the user knows the HASH id of a given content and also the source storing that content, he can make use of the **Get Resource** functionality, accessing directly the content as shown in Figure 3-16. This a prototype implementation of the P2PProtocol and should be refined in the future.

Figure 3-16. Protocol for having a direct access to the distributed resources

Once the user has downloaded locally the desired content, he can play it accordingly to the associated license. Figures 3-17 3-18 show the playing of a governed content published with a CreativeCommons license for non-commercial purpose. The former shows the disclaimer to be accepted by the user before starting the real play shown in the latter.

Figure 3-17. SAV user interface playing a digital item having a CreativeCommons License: the disclaimer

Figure 3-18. SAV user interface playing a digital item having a CreativeCommons License

Similarity search on DRM

Preface: *The following is the description of the innovative approach proposed by the author for managing IPR as digital features, applying a distance function for representing them in a metric space, enabling a new way for indexing digital rights [85, 86]*

4.1 Introduction

In the last years a multitude of devices able to consume and produce good-quality digital content has become accessible to a big part of the population, and the number of individuals, left aside the professionals, using them is exponentially growing. People from all over the world are creating images and audio/video files, and most of the times are happy to share them with others by means of electronic mail, web sites, chats, multimedia messaging services and several distributed systems.

Our cultural heritage is no longer made up of videos, images and text documents provided by “institutional” public or private bodies only, but also by every connected device as well.

However, people do start feeling the importance of associating rights information to the content created and released to the public for several reasons: for being attributed the ownership of the content, for allowing the content to be consumed only under some circumstances, to limit the usage of the content to a restricted set of users, just to mention a few.

In order to be able to guarantee the preservation and access of these digital items, we have to take into account the Digital Rights Management information associated with them during the creation phase and especially during the search of something provided by someone else.

Several approaches have been proposed so far for managing Digital Rights and many standards are available for representing them, but usually open as well as trusted systems provide a simple *attribute search* on a single specific type of license.

We are proposing here a different approach for indexing and searching the information related to the licenses of the digital items, towards a more flexible and interoperable environment.

4.2 Backgrounds

Many network infrastructures are arising in order to provide the bases for Web sharing and searching functionalities on digital items. Most of them are peered oriented networks, such as eMule [122] or BitTorrent [6] for images and audio/video files and Joost [123] for video streaming.

Furthermore there are several multimedia platforms which enable the automatic audio/video processing for cataloging and indexing digital items [124] that, in combination with the network infrastructure, will provide

powerful solutions for digital content management.

Before introducing the novel approach for dealing with DRM at query time, a number of related concepts are discussed in the following sections.

4.2.1 Digital Rights Management

The content items residing in most of network infrastructures mentioned above are currently not associated with Rights information, moreover service providers and users want to be aware of the license related to the searched content and want to know what are the actions that can be done on the downloaded digital items.

There are many standard initiatives that are trying to provide the basis for a DRM infrastructure, such as MPEG [125], OMA [126], DVB [127], DMP [90], Coral [128], TV-Anytime [129] as well as many proprietary solutions.

The DRM landscape is still very much fragmented, and it would be very challenging today to predict if, when and how there would be a standard and widely adopted DRM solution prevailing over the others, particularly in such an heterogeneous environment as the Web.

Fortunately the expression of the kind of the license is evolving in a more agreed way. Even if from the point of view of the copyright law there are still some differences between the license and the actions that a DRM system is able to provide according to that license, some standards on the expression of the license are arising and are commonly used. Anyway we have to point out the important difference between the *license*, a *statement concerning rights to use content* and the *enforcement* that the terms of the license are indeed followed by the user.

This chapter deals with the definition of the license and in particular the search capabilities of a digital item by its license. We do not want to provide any guideline nor implementation of the software for controlling the respect of use of the license as a DRM system has to guarantee. We want to provide an innovative approach for managing the license attributes in order to be able to search for a similar (as well as for different or not similar) digital object as query with its related digital license.

Up to now, a few solutions for expressing Rights information have been standardized, such as MPEG-21 Right Expression Language (REL) [88], Open Digital Right Language (ODRL) [130], TV-Anytime RMPI [131], Adobe Content Manager, [132], CreativeCommons (CC) [133], and Publishing Requirements for Industry Standard Metadata (PRISM) [134].

In this chapter we will concentrate on the digital items (mainly audio/video files) produced by individuals and professionals and made available on the Web with associated Rights information. Hence we are focusing our attention here on the language for expressing their licenses.

In order to be able to calculate a metric distance between licenses, a common Rights Expression language has to be chosen. In our analysis we adopted MPEG-21 REL for the following reason:

1. it is an ISO Standard;
2. it is widely considered the most flexible and powerful tool to digitally express rights;
3. several *profiles* of the REL standard have already been defined within MPEG: the Mobile And optical Media (MAM) [135], the Dissemination And Capture (DAC) [136] and the Open Release Content (ORC) [137] profiles;

4. it is being adopted as the default Rights Expression language in a number of standard specifications dealing with DRM issues such as in most Multimedia Application Formats (MAF) [138] specifications in MPEG and DMP Interoperable DRM Platform, as well as by several European IST Projects such as AXMEDIS [139].

The three REL profiles mentioned above were conceived for allowing the expression of MPEG-21 REL licenses able to express equivalent Rights expressions as OMA ODRL [140], TV-Anytime RMPI and CC licenses. Therefore it is possible to convert ODRL, RMPI and CC licenses into equivalent MPEG-21 REL licenses when governed content is ingested in the network considered in this paper. The similarity search algorithm can then be applied on content belonging to different application domains.

The full MPEG-21 REL standard has more functionalities than those supported by the three considered profiles: MAM, DAC and ORC. However, as a first step, we will focus on a subset of the language. The MPEG-21 REL schemas, although not having a normative value, are split into six different namespaces: *Core*, *Standard Extension*, *Multimedia Extension*, *Multimedia Extension 1*, *Multimedia Extension 2* and *Multimedia Extension 3*. The analysis described in this paper will be based on licenses validating against the six namespaces mentioned above but only containing the elements and complex types defined in the three profiles considered.

4.2.2 Similarity Search

The notion of similarity has been studied extensively in the field of psychology and has an important role in cognitive sciences. From a database prospective, similarity search is based on gradual rather than exact relevance. A distance between objects is used to quantify the proximity, similarity or dissimilarity of a query object versus the objects stored in a database to be searched.

A similarity search can be seen as a process of obtaining data objects in order of their distance or dissimilarity from a given query object. It is a kind of sorting, ordering, or ranking of objects with respect to the query object, where the ranking criterion is the distance measure.

Though this principle works for any distance measure, we restrict the possible set of measure to the metric distance. Because of the mathematical foundations of the metric space notion, partitioning and pruning rules can be constructed for developing efficient index structures. Therefore, in the past years the research has been focused on metric spaces [141].

4.3 The metric space approach

Although many similarity search approaches have been proposed, the most generic one considers the mathematical metric space as a suitable abstraction of similarity [141].

The simple but powerful concept of the metric space consists of a domain of objects and a distance function that measures the proximity of pairs of objects.

Let $M = (\mathcal{D}, d)$ be a metric space defined over a domain of objects \mathcal{D} and a total (distance) function $d : \mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. The following properties always hold in $M \forall x, y \in \mathcal{D}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x, y) &\geq 0 && \text{(non-negativity),} \\
 d(x, y) &= 0 \text{ iff } x = y && \text{(identity),} \\
 d(x, y) &= d(y, x) && \text{(symmetry),} \\
 d(x, z) &\leq d(x, y) + d(y, z) && \text{(triangle inequality).}
 \end{aligned}$$

The metric space approach has been proved to be very important for building efficient indexes for similarity searching. A survey of existing approaches for centralized structures (e.g. M-tree [142] and D-Index [143]) can be found in [141] and [144].

Very recently even scalable and distributed index structures based on Peer-to-Peer networks have also been proposed for similarity searching in metric spaces, i.e. GHT* [16], VPT* [145], MCAN [15], M-Chord [17] (see [145] for a comparison of their performances).

Currently many research projects are investigating these fields, such as SAPIR [146], a project funded by European Research Area in the 6th Framework Program, that aims to develop cutting-edge technology that will break the barriers and enable search engines to look for large scale audio-visual information by content, using the *query by example* paradigm. More details can be founded at Appendix A

4.4 The proposed solution of metric distance for license

It is worthwhile to underline that in order to be able to handle the Rights of digital contents, they should be defined during the creation phase of the items. Hence the GUI that a sharing system should provide has to take into account the multiple choice of available licenses.

Flickr [147] is currently providing at least one type of license definition (CreativeCommons). So far the search engine for the Rights is nothing but an attribute search, looking for the same value of a specific attribute of the expressed license.

We suggest that for enabling efficient and distributed queries on Digital Rights the metadata expressing the license can be considered as special features in a given space, instead of simple attributes. Hence we can perform the similarity search on Rights by finding out the appropriate distance function.

A typical REL license is composed of a number of *grants* and an *issuer*, the latter being the entity granting a *right* to the *principal*. Every grant, in turn, may still contain three main types of information: the principal, identifying whom a right is granted to; the right: an action that a principal may perform on the associated resource; and the resource, the *object* which the right in the grant applies to.

The simplified model of REL license has been shown in Figure 3-1 where some components are omitted for clarification purposes.

The *issuer*, in the most general case, could be seen as an element not adding significant value as a parameter in a search. However, there are some cases in which the lack of metadata describing the content item could make the information contained within the issuer element rather important. For instance, an issuer specialised in issuing licenses for a specific type of content could become a target for searches for that specific type.

The principal, as well as the right, are certainly very fundamental for any similarity search. If the target of a

search is the content having an associated license specifying a principal p_1 and a right r_1 , the result of the search not matching exactly (p_1, r_1) would certainly score bad in terms of distance from the search target. It has to be noted that in ORC licenses (those expressing in REL the CreativeCommons licenses) the principal is never specified, meaning that anyone is granted the rights specified by the license. All ORC licenses would immediately satisfy the principal requirement in a search. Instead, for all the cases in which the principal is a well defined entity (e.g. a *device* with a unique certificate, or a *domain* or a unique *user identifier* contained in a Smart/SIM Card), if this value doesn't match the same specified value, the result should certainly be interpreted as distant from the target. If a principal is specified in a license, this has a high relevance. In an open network it can be the only distinctive differentiating parameter and in a local network (e.g. a home domain) the principal can be used to identify one of a restricted number of users. Moreover, a number of content items may be governed by a license granting access only to users or devices belonging to a specific domain. In this case, in order to obtain more meaningful results, it is important that when a similarity search is performed, the principal parameter contains all the *identities* a user has, including, for instance, any domain to which the user has subscribed. In some circumstances, a user may have the opportunity to join a domain or obtain a license for a content item at a later stage, therefore even if the license of a content item does not grant a right specifically for the principal being searched, the user may become a valid principal in the future, hence the result of the search could get an high score in terms of distance even if the principal found is not the same as the principal searched for.

The same applies to the right; if the right found is not the same as the right searched for, the distance from the optimal result is certainly high. However, if the user has the chance to acquire the specific right he is looking for at a later stage, the distance would be reduced. Those specifications supporting the super-distribution model, such as ISO/IEC MPEG Media Streaming MAF standard [138], as well as the DMP IDP [90], enable specifying in the content item itself the location from where a license can be obtained, therefore if this information is present, it must be considered as a key factor.

Finally, the *conditions* under which a principal may exercise a right may play a decisive role, too. Only if all conditions in a license are fully met, a right can be exercised. While some conditions are deal-breaking (e.g. the geographical location in which a content item can be played: either the user is in that area or he is not), others may still be acceptable by the user even if they are not the preferred choice.

We propose in Figure 4-1 an example of Rights and Conditions for DAC and ORC profiles where the candidate attributes to be compared are reported. Rights can be represented mainly by binary attributes, while Conditions include also numerical and textual attributes.

4.4.1 IPR-based distance functions

In this section we analyse the problem of defining a metric distance (i.e., a dissimilarity measure) between two licenses. We focus on comparing two licenses considering only the information related to the principal expressed in the query. For simplicity we will not consider the issuer in searching for similarity.

However, it would be easy to modify the defined distance taking in consideration also the issuer and assigning a greater distance value to those license having different issuers. Thus, the distance is evaluated considering the rights and conditions that are associated with a given principal in both licenses.

Let \mathcal{D} be the domain of metadata related to the license of any given object. For any object $x \in \mathcal{D}$ we use the following notation:

DAC		ORC	
Rights	Conditions	Rights	Conditions
possessProperty	validityInterval	possessProperty	territory
governedCopy	exerciseLimit	execute	drmSystem
governedMove	territory	play	derivationConstraint
derive	validityIntervalFloating	print	outputRegulation
execute	validityTimeMetered	modify	seekPermission
play	outputRegulation	adapt	startCondition
print	seekPermission	delist	copyrightNotice
enlist	startCondition	enlist	nonCommercialUse
delist	simultaneousAccess	governedCopy	sourceCode
drmSystem	noSkipConstraint	governedMove	
export	destinationPrincipal	aggregate	
extendRights	destinationCondition	embed	
	securitySystem	governedAdapt	
	proximity	governedAggregate	
	scrambling	governedEmbed	
	timedExerciseLimit		
	timeShiftDuration		

Figure 4-1. Example of Rights and Conditions for DAC and ORC profiles.

- r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{n_r} are the n_r possible rights;
- c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{n_c} are the n_c possible conditions;
- $x_{i,1}, x_{i,2}, \dots, x_{i,n_c}$ are the n_c condition values for the i -th right.

We define the global distance $d(x, y) \in [0, 1]$ as the weighted sum of the distances between the rights, i.e.

$$d(x, y) = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^{n_r} w_j} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n_r} w_i \cdot d_{r_i}(x, y) \quad (4.1)$$

where $d_{r_i}(x, y) \in [0, 1]$ is the distance between the two licence considering the i -th right,

and w_i are weights used to give more or less importance to the various rights.

Note that $\sum_{j=1}^{n_r} w_j$ normalize the distance between 0 and 1.

We define the distance $d_{r_i}(x, y) \in [0, 1]$ between two license x and y considering only the right r_i as:

- $d_{r_i}(x, y) = 0$, if r_i is not present in both licences;
- $d_{r_i}(x, y) = 1$, if r_i is present only in one license;

- $d_{r_i}(x, y) = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^{n_c} w_{i,j}} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{n_c} w_{i,j} \cdot d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}),$

otherwise (i.e. if the right is present in both licences).

$d_{c_j} \in [0, 1]$ is the distance between the j -th conditions for the right i in the two licenses,

while $w_{i,j}$ are weights used to give more or less importance to the various rights.

Note that $\sum_{j=1}^{n_c} w_{i,j}$ normalize the distance between 0 and 1.

Once a general definition of a distance function is given, the actual computation of the distance $d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j})$ between two values $x_{i,j}$ and $y_{i,j}$ of the j -th condition must be defined considering the specific attribute type. To define this distance we must deal with the fact that the given condition could be not associated with the given right in one or both of the licenses.

Thus, while the distance between two conditions of the same type must be defined considering the type of the condition (see next sections), all the condition distances must follow two rules:

- $d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) = 0$, if c_j for the right r_i is not specified in both the license x and y ;
- $d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) = d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, u_{c_j})$, if c_j for the right r_i is specified in only one (x) of the two licenses. u_{c_j} is the most unrestrictive value for condition c_j .

In fact, if the condition is not present it means that it is not necessary.

We now give some example of distances for specific condition types.

4.4.1.1 Binary conditions

In many cases conditions are expressed by binary values, describing whether or not a given condition is necessary for the given right.

In this case (i.e. $x_{i,j}, y_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$)

we can use the L_1 norm, which assumes binary values as well. Hence the distance is directly computed as:

$$d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) = |x_{i,j} - y_{i,j}| = x_{i,j} \oplus y_{i,j}. \quad (4.2)$$

Please note that a specific weight to this distance can be given by setting $w_{i,j}$. Obviously, for binary value $u_{c_j} = 0$.

4.4.1.2 Numeric conditions

For conditions expressed with a number (i.e., $x_{i,j}, y_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}$), which for example can represent a fee for accessing the digital content, it is possible to apply the L_1 norm or the euclidian distance.

However, more sophisticated metric distances could be used for specific numerical attributes. For instance, we suggest to define the distance between fees as:

$$d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) = \alpha |\log(x_{i,j}) - \log(y_{i,j})| , \quad (4.3)$$

or

$$d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) = \alpha \left| \log \left(\frac{x_{i,j}}{y_{i,j}} \right) \right| \quad (4.4)$$

where α is a normalization factor.

According to Equation 4.4, the distance between \$5 and \$10 is the same as the distance between two fees of \$50 and \$100 respectively.

We believe that given a fee as query, the user is interested on the proportion between its query and any given fee. Unfortunately in this case any non \$0 fees would be at infinite distance from \$0 objects.

Incidentally, in the case of fees this characteristics may reflect a common attitude, because users that are looking for free digital content are not interested in non free items. For instance, they are not willing (or able) to purchase items on the Web, or they are browsing for material just because it is free.

Anyway, to avoid this problem we suggest that whenever the fee value is smaller than a given threshold, say \$0.01, the value used for evaluating the distance is automatically set to 0.01 (which is also used value for u_{c_j}).

In this way, the distance between \$0 and \$1 becomes the same of the distance between \$1 and \$100, which is a reasonable assumption. It is worth noting that the distance is still a metric.

To keep the distance in $[0, 1]$ we do not only need a minimum but also a maximum for the fees. Thus, for evaluating a distance between two fees we will limit the fee value.

Anything above this limit will be considered, only for distance evaluating purposing, as having the given limit as value. The α then will be $|\log(MIN) - \log(MAX)|$.

It should also be noted that there are other possible approaches for measuring differences in prices, for example the *gap-ratio* computed by the following equation:

$$d_{c_j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) = \frac{x_{i,j} - y_{i,j}}{y_{i,j}} . \quad (4.5)$$

Yet, the gap-ratio is not symmetric and thus it cannot be used for

the proposed metric approach.

4.4.1.3 Term based conditions

For conditions whose value is a term from a given vocabulary, we propose a specific approach. If the j -th attribute of the i -th group is a term taken from a specific vocabulary of m terms, we can define the distance $d_{i,j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j})$ between the two values according to what reported in Table 4-1 where $term_0$ is used as

u_{c_j} (i.e. whenever the given condition is not specified).

In this way it is possible to define a specific distance between any given term and a not specified condition.

	$term_0$	$term_1$	$term_2$...	$term_m$
$term_0$	0	$\alpha_{1,0}^{i,j}$	$\alpha_{2,0}^{i,j}$...	$\alpha_{m,0}^{i,j}$
$term_1$	$\alpha_{0,1}^{i,j}$	0	$\alpha_{2,1}^{i,j}$...	$\alpha_{m,1}^{i,j}$
$term_2$	$\alpha_{0,2}^{i,j}$	$\alpha_{1,2}^{i,j}$	0	...	$\alpha_{m,2}^{i,j}$
...
$term_m$	$\alpha_{0,m}^{i,j}$	$\alpha_{1,m}^{i,j}$	$\alpha_{2,m}^{i,j}$...	0

Table 4-1. Distance values for attributes taken from terms in a given dictionary

It is assumed that the values of α are manually chosen according to the semantic of the given terms. For $d_{i,j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j})$ to be a metric the matrix must be symmetric, thus $\alpha_{a,b}^{i,j} = \alpha_{b,a}^{i,j}$, all the diagonal values must be 0 and

$$\forall l, \alpha_{a,b}^{i,j} \leq \alpha_{a,l}^{i,j} + \alpha_{l,b}^{i,j}. \quad (4.6)$$

A user interface should help the administrator setting the α values according to these requirements. A trivial solution is to set all $\alpha_{a,b}^{i,j} = 1$ when $a \neq b$, and in this case textual attributes are considered as binary attributes.

4.4.1.4 Distance for sets

For conditions that have sets as value we suggest to use the *Jaccard's coefficient* (which is a metric). Assuming two sets $x_{i,j}$ and $y_{i,j}$, *Jaccard's coefficient* is defined as follows:

$$d(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) = 1 - \frac{x_{i,j} \cap y_{i,j}}{x_{i,j} \cup y_{i,j}}. \quad (4.7)$$

For conditions based on sets we suggest to use the empty set as u_{c_j} .

4.4.1.5 Metric distance

We now prove that if all the distances used to compare the values of each right are metric, the proposed distance between two licenses is still metric. In other words, a weighted sum of metric distances is a metric distance too. In fact, $\forall x, y \in \mathcal{D}$ and for any given right $i = 1, \dots, n_r$ and condition $\forall j = 1, \dots, n_c$ we get:

$$d_{i,j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) \leq d_{i,j}(x_{i,j}, z_{i,j}) + d_{i,j}(z_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) \Rightarrow$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} w_{i,j} \cdot d_{i,j}(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}) \leq$$

$$\leq \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} w_{i,j} \cdot [d_{i,j}(x_{i,j}, z_{i,j}) + d_{i,j}(z_{i,j}, y_{i,j})] \Rightarrow$$

$$d(x, y) \leq d(x, z) + d(z, y).$$

Thus, if all the distances defined for the conditions are metric, the proposed distance is metric too.

4.5 Significant use cases

Searching for a digital item can be done by similarity search and/or by textual attributes. For example we can look for an image or a sound similar to what someone provided as query to the search engine. Moreover we can add to our query some keywords that the search engine will take into account as specific attributes. Nowadays most of the search engines available on the web are providing nothing but the “full text” and/or “attribute” search capabilities.

Even if many research projects are developing audio and image “similarity” search, the only approach concerning the licenses is based on attributes.

Instead, according to our proposal, a user will be able for example to search for an image similar to the one provided considering both the multimedia content (content base) and the related license (provided by the user as well). Furthermore the user can apply for searching similar images regarding the multimedia content and a specific kind of license defined by mean of attributes.

In Figure 4-2 we are pointing out that the *similarity search use case* is made up of the inclusion of two distinct use cases described below, respectively the similarity search on multimedia features and the similarity search on IPR features. We have to consider the IPR features as all the possible attributes expressing a license. Focusing our attention to MPEG-21 REL the IPR features could be considered as example as all the attributes available for expressing the issuer, the principal, the rights and conditions. Hence the user can either provide a REL license (conforming to MAM, DAC or ORC profiles), or a list of attributes expressing the search criteria to the algorithm performing the search. We can figure out at least the following use cases dealing with images:

1. the user is searching for images similar to a given one both considering its visual appearance and the provided license
2. the user is searching for images similar to a given one but with specific license “attributes”

In the first use case, let’s consider as an example a user interested in an artistic image for his desktop. Let’s also suppose that he finds a low resolution image on the Web of a painting whose he does not know who the painter is.

If the user is interested in acquiring the same picture with higher quality, he could perform a query using

Figure 4-2. Use case diagram for similarity search

the system described in this paper by providing in input the low quality image and the desired Rights information, expressed in this case as an ORC license. The search engine will display as a result the ranking list of images similar in terms of “pixels” and Rights information to the one provided. For example a result could be a picture of the same painting made by a tourist and released according to a CreativeCommons license and another result, probably distant from the previous in the result list, could be the photograph of the painting made by a professional photographer having an attached license expressed in MPEG-21 REL, expressing for example the price for downloading the high resolution picture. The user can then choose among the two results, according to both the quality of the image in the result list and the kind of license, having immediately the feeling of how far is the result from the provided object query.

In the second use case the user is able to identify objects stored in the network that are very similar to those provided in the query, but for example with a different license.

Imagine a professional photographers agency that wants to be sure that nobody is using their own pictures in an illicit way. The agency can query the system by providing the picture to be searched and the attributes of an open license or something “similar” to an open one.

If the system finds a result, it means either that someone has made the same picture or that someone is sharing an unauthorized copy of the picture. This use case is innovative because the current search engines are focused on content sharing without addressing the “control” of the content itself, delegating this feature entirely to the DRM systems.

Conclusions

In this thesis we have presented the analysis and design of an interoperable digital rights management system working on structured overlay networks (actually distributed hash tables).

The work has been presented at several international conferences and has been described in documents and papers written by the author in collaboration with the following research projects and initiatives: SAPIR, DMP and DMIN.it as well as the internal research projects at EURIX S.r.l.

In **Chapter 1** we have analyzed the trust and security in Peer-to-Peer networks for the management of governed digital contents in SAPIR environment and we have provided a survey of the available technologies in this field. The main security concerns for a Peer-to-Peer systems have been discussed based on relevant approaches available in the literature. An analysis of efficient ways for spam prevention and for trust enforcement in Peer-to-Peer systems has been presented, based on the different approaches which are currently under discussion in the scientific community.

In **Chapter 2** we have presented the requirements and specification of an *Interoperable Digital Rights Management System*, according to the guidelines proposed by the Digital Media Projects.

The outcomes of this work have been published in DMP documents and are currently under review and update. These specifications make up the building blocks of the prototype implementation discussed in Chapter 3.

In **Chapter 3** we have presented a suitable approach for indexing and searching structured metadata related to digital rights on a DHT. Digital rights information is expressed according to MPEG-21 REL and a solution for indexing structured information on a flat space has been proposed.

The creation of a distributed index in a structured overlay networks allows an efficient distribution and retrieval of relevant metadata. The right management warrantee has been deeply studied in the last few years and lots of solutions are available. However a reliable solution concerning the retrieval of the license associated to the digital items is still missing. The approach proposed, based on the standard expression language used to express licenses of digital items, allows the experimentation of advanced techniques, such as the similarity search , also for IPR features.

In **Chapter 4** we have proposed an innovative approach for indexing and searching content items based on their associated Rights information expressed in MPEG-21 Rights Expression Language according to specific profiles of this standard. The metadata shown are taken as examples and should be changed to fit

with the needs of the software infrastructure that the user have to deal with.

This approach is considering the IPR attributes as *special features* to which can be applied a specific distance function that can also be metric, enabling efficient querying on different IPR schema representation and complex Right Expression structures.

Although several organizations are dealing with the expression of Rights information, not so much has been done so far concerning the "retrieval" of the license associated to the digital items.

The proposed approach does not claim to cover all possible Rights statements and expression languages available nowadays. However, by selecting a joint of the three MPEG-21 REL profiles mentioned above, the solution will indeed support a large number of use cases. Furthermore we can also have a ranking list of results according to the metric function, by defining the distance between the license attributes and by a mapping between license types that the user have to manage.

As the "distance" between licenses can not be interpreted as an absolute value, but depends on the specific user and the circumstances in which a search is made, by adding software agents able to determining the value of the "weights" in the proposed algorithm may very well bring even more accurate search results, personalized on the bases of user preferences and context information.

Acronyms

ACL	Access Control List
ADSL	Asymmetric Digital Subscriber Line
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
API	Application Programming Interface
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CAN	Content Addressable Network
CC	Creative Commons
CCD	Content Creation Device
CID	Content Identification Device
CPD	Content Provider Device
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRC	Cyclic Redundancy Check
DAC	Dissemination And Capture
DBMS	Data Base Management System
DCI	DMP Content Information
DCF	DMP Content File
DHT	Distributed Hash Table
DID	Device Item Declaration
DII	Digital Item Identification
DIS	Digital Item Streaming
DMD	Domain Management Device
DMIN.it	Digital Media in Italy
DMP	Digital Media Project
DMZ	Demilitarized Zone
DRM	Digital Right Management
DVB-T/H	Digital Video Broadcasting Terrestrial/Handheld

GHT	Generalized Hyperplane Tree
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
iDRM	interoperable Digital Right Management
IDP	Interoperable DRM Platform
IP	Internet Protocol
IPMP	Intellectual Property Management and Protection
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JDK	Java Development Kit
LAN	Local Area Network
LPD	License Provider Device
MAF	Multimedia Application Format
MAM	Mobile And optical Media
MCAN	Metric Content Addressable Network
MD5	Message Digest 5 (one way hash function)
MPEG	Moving Picture Expert Group
MPL	Mozilla Public Licence
MPQF	MPEG Query Format
NAT	Network Address Translation
ODRL	Open Digital Right Language
OMA	Open Mobile Alliance
OODB	Object Oriented Data Base
ORC	Open Release Content
OSS	Open Source Software
PAN	Personal Area Network
PGP	Pretty Good Privacy
PIN	Personal Identification Number
PRISM	Publishing Requirements for Industry Standard Metadata
P2P	Peer-to-Peer

REL	Right Expression Language
RMI	Remote Method Invocation
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RSA	Rivest, Shamir, Adleman (public key encryption technology)
SAV	Stationary Audio Video Device
SEDA	Staged, Event-Driven Architecture
SHA-1	SHA-1 Secure Hashing Algorithm 1
SON	Structured Overlay Networks
SSL	Secure Socket Layer
UMID	Unique Material Identifier (SMPTE)
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UML	Universal Unique Identifier
UX	User eXperience
WAN	Wide Area Network
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

A

SAPIR

SAPIR [146] stands for Search in Audio-Visual Content using P2P Information Retrieval.

The project intends to propose new solutions for an innovative technological infrastructure for next-generation Multimedia Search Engines.

This research effort should lead towards a distributed, P2P based, search engine architecture, as opposed to today parallel search engines within a centralized Web data warehouse.

Web search is dominated today by search giants (Google, Yahoo, MSN) that utilize text indexes and page rank algorithms based on incoming html links. Consequently, search in audio-visual content which spans across most of web data is limited to associated text and metadata annotations. This requires the user to formulate her needs for audio-visual content using text that she believes best describes the object of search. The problem is emphasized in outdoor environments using mobile devices with limited data entry capabilities.

SAPIR aims to develop cutting-edge technology that will break the barriers and enable search engines to search large scale audio-visual information by content using the query by example paradigm.

A picture is worth a thousand words so if people could use images taken by their cell phone as query input to find information about the flower they stumbled across or sing a melody they once heard and get back the full song into their iPod this would make searches and life much easier.

The main architecture is shown in Figure A-1

Audio-visual content indexing and searching by similarity call for a scalable distributed P2P environment which is not possible today by centralized search solutions such as Google and its likes. SAPIR will provide a P2P system where people serve as peers for publishing their content and for searching by defining user needs as combination of text and real audio-visual content. Having such a technology can give significant advantage to the European community over existing centralized text-only search engines and can be applied in various fields of applications such as tourism, government services, healthcare and more. For example, assume implementation of SAPIR in Europe where each city is a Peer, holding city-related information about its monuments, guided tours information, calendar of events etc. Tourists entering the city could use their cell phones or PDAs or even rent a mobile device and then receive tourism information nuggets based on pictures taken by their cell phones combined with personal interests, cultural origin, physical position, and activity history. This can increase revenues for Telco providers, for content-provider peers through advertising promotions and improve local economy by increasing tourism incomes.

SAPIR technology will additionally break the silo of centralized search services which only very few giants can afford, and provide a more scalable distributed approach that can build on resources provided by smaller companies and thus make search technology and its benefits available to more companies world-wide.

SAPIR intends to propose new solutions for an innovative technological infrastructure for next-generation Multimedia Search Engines. This research effort should lead towards a distributed, P2P based, search engine architecture, as opposed to today parallel search engines within a centralized Web data warehouse.

Figure A-1. Overview of the SAPIR project architecture

The P2P architecture will be exploited both at indexing and at query time. During indexing, SAPIR aims at investigating a novel distributed push-based crawling model, where content providers publish and push information to the P2P indexing nodes instead of being visited by crawling agents. The CPU load required by media specific analyzers for feature extraction can then be distributed between Peers thus exploiting the P2P architecture.

At query time, novel query routing algorithm will be developed to route a query to the peers which have the best probability to find best results for the query

B

DMP

DMP [90] stands for Digital Media Project. Follows a brief description taken from the DMP statute (ART.3) [148].

The DMP is a not-for-profit organisation with the mission to promote continuing successful development, deployment and use of Digital Media that respect the rights of creators and rights holders to exploit their works, the wish of end users to fully enjoy the benefits of Digital Media and the interests of various value-chain players to provide products and services, according to the principles laid down in the Digital Media Manifesto.

Digital Media includes new emerging experiences made possible by Information and Communication Technologies along with mainstream media experiences such as Compact Disc, Digital Versatile Disc, Digital Audio Broadcasting and Digital Television.

DMP operates on the basis of open international collaboration of all interested parties: corporations and individual firms, partnerships, governmental bodies or international organisations, supporting the DMP mission and the means to achieve its goals. The terms are reasonable and applied uniformly and openly. DMP seeks the involvement of creators and end users of Digital Media through appropriate mechanisms.

The goals of DMP are realised through the development of Technical Specifications and Recommended Practices enabling businesses that support new or improved user experiences, and Recommended Actions to appropriate entities to act on removal of barriers holding up exploitation of Digital Media. Technical Specifications, Recommended Practices and Recommended Actions are collectively called "DMP Approved Documents". DMP contributes the results of its activities to appropriate formal standards bodies and other appropriate entities whenever this is instrumental to achieve the general DMP goals.

The business of DMP shall not be conducted for the financial profits of its Members but for their mutual benefits. Discussions about sales levels, methods, channels of distribution, markets, customers, prices or profitability or any other topic which would restrict use of Digital Media are prohibited.

C

DMIN.it

Digital Media in Italia (dmin.it) [78] is a grassroots non-profit organisation established in November 2005 with the goal to identify action areas that enable Italy to acquire a primary position in the exploitation of the global digital media phenomenon.

Follows a quick overview of the project taken from the report written on 30 September 2007 [149]

In September 2006 dmin.it published its proposal [150]. Its stated objective is maximisation of the flow of digital media. These are defined as content that is digital, can be transported on digital networks, can be processed by programmable hardware and presented on a variety of inexpensive devices. The document proposes to achieve the objective by acting on the ways content is offered, accessed via broadband networks and paid for by supporting two fundamental, albeit often antithetic, requirements: freedom of action for entrepreneurs and freedom to post/access content for creators/consumers.

The first leg of the dmin.it proposal is based on an interoperabile Digital Rights Management specification that dmin.it calls iDRM. Dmin.it has selected IDP-3.0 as its iDRM because the specification is public, implemented in Open Source Software (Chillout [82]), is accessible by anybody, open to innovative business models that support all legitimate intermediation roles, particularly those that do not require Technical Protection Measures (TPM).

Dmin.it is working to make iDRM adopted at the national level with the intention of creating the conditions in which the service provider which employs a proprietary DRM technology (pDRM) to offer content for which it has rights for a given distribution channel shall also offer it on the same distribution channel using the iDRM technology at conditions that are fair and non discriminatory compared with the conditions used for the pDRM offer.

The iDRM specification (in English), proposed legislation (in Italian) and the proposed governance (in Italian) can be found in [81], [151] and [77] respectively.

The set up is depicted in the figure C-1

The second leg of the proposal which dmin.it calls iNet gives full freedom to a broadband network operator to offer the type of access to its network that is most congenial to its business model. However, the broadband network operator has the obligation to provide any network user a content provider, an intermediary or end user requesting it the raw service-agnostic access to the "Big Internet with the technical features of the native operator offer. The access is provided at conditions that are fair and non discriminatory compared with the conditions used for the native access offer.

Moreover broadband network operators must guarantee network service interoperability by agreeing between them and providing specific Quality of Service (QoS) levels at peering points so as to provide network users with appropriate QoS levels.

Figure C-1. *The iDRM leg of the dmin.it proposal*

The iNet specification and proposed legislation (both in Italian) can be found in [152] and [153], respectively. The governance is being developed.

The set up is depicted in the figure C-2

Figure C-2. *The iNet leg of the dmin.it proposal*

Lastly the third leg of the proposal which dmin.it calls iPay foresees that any party complying with banking regulations may offer Virtual Account services that are interoperable with the services offered by other operators. Accounts are virtual because they are not denominated in a real currency but in points, units, or credits and used for transactions connected with the use of digital media.

Each Virtual Account is supported by one or more guaranteed payment systems in a real currency (e.g. bank account, credit card, prepaid card, electronic purse etc.). Transactions are performed between Virtual Accounts. However, synchronisation of a Virtual Account with its supporting payment system is performed only periodically or on request to decrease real money transaction costs.

The iPay specification (in Italian) can be found in [154]. The proposed legislation and governance are being developed.

The set up is depicted in the figure C-3

Figure C-3. *The iPay leg of the dmin.it proposal*

In general the advantages of the dmin.it proposal are:

- Creation of a homogeneous market of content, network and payment systems with 60 million creators/consumers capable of supporting the business of even small-to-medium size companies operating in content value-chains;
- Lowering the access threshold to value-chains, e.g. to creators who can easily distribute their content with the possibility to be remunerated, something that today is not easy;
- Possibility to set up new value-chains with new intermediaries who can plug in to them; Incentivation of content consumption because of the large number of content and services accessible using devices available on the open market;
- Disincentivation of the use of improperly obtained content because rights are managed or enforced in a transparent, flexible and fair although rigorous manner;
- Reduction of technology cost thanks to an open market where several competing suppliers offer solution based on standard components;
- Exportability of models by companies that will experiment with the business opportunities in the new national market;
- Increased visibility of Italian digital media to promote the Italian lifestyle, with positive fallouts on Italian culture, tourism, fashion, food etc.

The advanced stage of development of the various components of the dmin.it proposal has prompted dmin.it to enter a new phase aimed at actually implementing and deploying several practical examples (use cases). Currently this is the list of solutions being developed using the technologies described above:

- VHS 2.0: a system where a user can record video sources in an encrypted format so that he can be sure that he is the only one able to watch the recorded videos
- P2P iDRM: a P2P network where users can upload and share in a governed but unprotected form their user-generated content and record companies can offer in a viral environment their catalogue in a governed format, either protected or unprotected (this use case is inspired by Use Case and Value Chain No. 6 of [75])
- idDRM: a system where confidential documents can be developed in a collaborative fashion. A project leader initiates a document and assigns to contributors the appropriate rights to act on the document
- iIPTV: a system that will eventually become a full implementation of an IPTV head end and set top boxes based on [138]
- ipDRM: making DMP SAVs by porting Chillout to portable/mobile devices (e.g. Nokia 800)
- Porting of Chillout to set top boxes: ditto for set top boxes
- Implicit and item-based recommendation system

Dmin.it has endorsed Chillouts OSS philosophy and is releasing the reference software of its specification and some demo applications (<http://wiki.dmin.it/>) in OSS.

D

Chillout

Chillout© [82] is the reference software implementation of the iDRM defined by DMP. Follows a quick overview of Chillout taken from the document dmp1045. Additional information about DMP and Chillout can be obtained from <http://www.dmpf.org/> and <http://chillout.dmpf.org/>. To join DMP contact secretariat@dmpf.org.

Started in 2003 as a non-profit organisation the DMP has realised that Digital Rights Management (DRM) is the technology that, if appropriately standardised, can cure many of the undesired side-effects of the direct use of digital technologies for media. Really? Is this not like swimming against the tide? Well, there are a few differences from what others call DRM. The first is that the DRM advocated by the DMP is interoperable, the second that it does what the word implies, namely it lets users manage content in a value chain, and the third that there are basic caveats to be kept in mind:

1. DRM must be end user friendly, i.e. absolutely transparent from the very first moment or end users will choose the hard-to-beat competition on the net. A standard DRM achieves exactly that.
2. DRM is not about photocopying old business models. Digital media has been synonymous with empowered imagination. DRM is not the technology to emasculate it and let everybody return to business as usual. A DRM standard lets people engage in new legitimate businesses.
3. DRM is not just about protection. DRM is seen by some as the technology to restrict, while DRM can enable value chains with many rights management modalities, ranging from content released with a licence requiring enforcement to a Creative Commons licence that does not require it. A DRM standard is not a technology to dictate business models, but a business tool to find common ground among parties, especially end users.
4. DRM is about enabling all legitimate value chain roles.

A DRM standard lets users create and distribute content while providing a core environment of mutual trust, including the ability to take on any role required of them by the value chains they are part of. A DRM standard is not a technology to exclude but a business tool to federate legitimate players.

DMP has recently approved version 3.0 of its specification, called Interoperable DRM Platform (IDP-3.0). As the name implies, the IDP is a platform, i.e. a middleware call it the digital media operating system on top of which all types of digital media value chains can be set up and operated. IDP-3.0 is broadly based on

the ISO MPEG-21 standard with the addition of a few additional technologies not available in the MPEG suite of standards.

Chillout© is the name given by the DMP to the IDP reference software. Released as Open Source Software (OSS) under the Mozilla Public Licence v. 1.1, Chillout is catered to by a growing international community and is being translated across major programming languages.

The layers of Chillout are depicted in Figure D-1:

Figure D-1. *Chillout Layers*

The functions of Chillout layers are:

1. Core library: a normative library of classes providing the functionalities needed to:
 - Represent: a set of classes to generate and parse the XML structures defined by the IDP;
 - Package: a set of classes to generate and parse files and streams for transport across devices;
 - Protocols: a set of classes to generate and parse messages exchanged by two Devices performing the protocols, and providing the functionality to send and receive such messages
2. Auxiliary library: a non-normative library of classes encapsulating the functionalities of a number of modules which a (hardware or software) device may have. In real devices, these modules could well be replaced by proprietary ones. However the interfaces of some components of this library may become part of the IDP. Examples are:
 - Security manager: module incorporating all those functionalities such as secure storage of digital certificates and licenses, performing signature operations, etc.
 - DRM Processor: module parsing DRM information, instantiating and managing the required DRM tools, etc.
3. Applications: a non-normative set of sample applications serving as
 - Examples of classes in the Core and Auxiliary libraries
 - Demonstrators of devices
 - Applications to test implementations of Represent, Package and Protocols classes.

As part of its mission the DMP has contributed some of its results to ISO. MPEG is in the process of standardising the Media Streaming Application Format completed in October 2007 as ISO/IEC 23000-5 [138]. This will be the first international standard for governed content applicable to such application domains as broadcasting and IPTV.

Figure D-2. Model of Media Streaming Application Format [138]

Other digital media related organisations have adopted IDP-3.0 and Chillout. One of them is Digital Media in Italia (<http://www.dmin.it/>). Dmin.it has endorsed Chillouts OSS philosophy and is releasing the reference software of its specification and some demo applications (<http://wiki.dmin.it/>) in OSS.

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